

D5.3: Gender Benchmarking Report

A Guide to Gender Benchmarking for Policy Related to Women-Led Rural and Farm Innovation

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¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive.

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge Innovation System
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CoP	Community of Practice
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ISMEA	Institute of Services for the Agricultural Food Market
LAG	Local Action Group
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
STEM	Science Technology Engineering Maths
WBA	World Benchmarking Alliance
WP	Work Package
Project partners	
Galway	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY
TU Delft	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY
UNICAL	UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA
LWL	LONGFORD WOMEN S LINK CLG
UTU	TURUN YLIOPISTO
UL	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
CE	CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL
HNEE	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE
ELARD	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE LEADER POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL
UOULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
ECOLISE	RESEAU EUROPEEN POUR DES INITIATIVES COMMUNAUTAIRES SUR LES CHANGEMENTS CLIMATIQUES ET LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE
MENDELU	MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNE
LNU	LINNEUNIVERSITETET
HLK	HOGSKOLAN FOR LARANDE OCH KOMMUNIKATION I JONKOPING - HLK SCHOOL OF EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

HIGHLIGHTS

Policy benchmarking needs to be better understood: The effectiveness of benchmarking as a policy assessment and learning tool needs to be better understood. There are different approaches to how policy benchmarking can be carried out as well as room for more detailed guidance on what different approaches offer. These guidelines aim to build understanding of policy benchmarking in the specific context of women-led rural and farm innovation.

Policy benchmarking is challenging: The guidelines outline key challenges that need to be considered when benchmarking policy and to improve the quality of benchmarking outcomes. The FLIARA focus has been on exploring how to strengthen qualitative approaches to policy benchmarking, an area that existing research and thinking on benchmarking suggests is important to develop. Benchmarking faces conundrums that present challenges to consider when benchmarking policy.

Benchmarking frameworks are important: The framework used to benchmark within is very important. It is the key to how policy performance is measured and the scope of the results the benchmarking will generate. Benchmarking frameworks can also be built so they can be applied in different ways. They can be designed to be flexible to allow room so that only specific themes of the framework are used to conduct benchmarking exercises. The **FLIARA Benchmarking Framework** is built with this consideration in mind.

Benchmarking as a wider process is important: Benchmarking results can provide valuable comparative assessment of policy performance. These results are just however potentially one, initial part of what benchmarking offers as a policy improvement tool. Benchmarking needs to avoid the tendency to look for a set of universal solutions. The wider learning from understanding policy practices and wider policy frameworks from other contexts is where the more specific ideas for future policy improvement can come from. However, harnessing this wider learning also needs to be actively built into the benchmarking process.

Recommendations for next steps: The benchmarking journey taken by FLIARA has also revealed how complex and challenging benchmarking can be. We also make a series of recommendations on how benchmarking can be better harnessed as a policy improvement tool and areas for future policy-focused research in this space. This includes pointing to the potential in benchmarking as a multi-actor policy improvement tool, where there is collaboration and co-creation of benchmarking, with the end goal of policy learning and improvement.

1. INTRODUCTION

“...benchmarking is not as straightforward – or as benign – as it is often claimed to be” (Arrowsmith et al., 2004, p. 312).

Benchmarking originated in the corporate world, meaning it has proven application in organisational contexts. It has long been used as a tool for comparison of companies on different business competitiveness measures in order to identify the highest performers (Bruno et al. 2006; Fagerberg, 2003). Benchmarking in a corporate context can include benchmarking company performance in relation to gender equality. For example, the World Benchmarking Alliance’s (WBA) Gender Benchmarking Methodology covers six areas impacting gender inequality: Governance and strategy; representation; compensation and benefits; health and well-being; violence and harassment; and marketplace and community (WBA, 2024).

The use of benchmarking as a tool in policy contexts can integrate lessons from benchmarking applications in the corporate arena. As argued by Arrowsmith et al. (2004), for companies benchmarking provides a tool for organisational learning through comparison. For policy benchmarking the learning principle is also central and comparison is the method that generates learning. Debate however exists on how well benchmarking can be transferred from contexts that compare performance in terms of one unit of analysis with defined boundaries (i.e. an organisation) to more complex systems, such as a policy context that is dynamic, multi-layered and context embedded (e.g. Arrowsmith et al., 2004; Navarro et al., 2013). Difficulties start to emerge when comparisons are presented as outcome and where comparative scoring of performance is emphasised. As Arrowsmith et al. (2004) also note benchmarking runs the risk of becoming a checking or verification exercise that results in a competitive ranking positioning companies on a league table, rather than an exercise of learning and doing things differently based on the results.

As discussed in this guide, benchmarking does have shortcomings, but it also has strengths that warrant further exploration to understand how best to use it as a tool for policy improvement. The FLIARA project has worked to explore how benchmarking can be improved and more often used in building a stronger policy system to support women-led rural and farm innovation. The wider value of policy benchmarking remains subject to ongoing debate. For example: “...the extent of its effectiveness as a policy learning tool and its practical applications remain understudied” (Dominique et al. 2013, p.506). This report aims to contribute to taking a step forward in this domain in the specific context of applying policy benchmarking in gender equality contexts and improving policies to better support women-led rural and farm innovation.

This report emerges from FLIARA Work Package (WP) 5 on Policy Design and Assessment. It serves to bring together and follow on from work carried out in WP1, WP3

and WP4. This report assesses the state of current policy benchmarking and provides a set of guidelines for policy benchmarking. The report provides general guidelines, while also developing a specific framework that provides a guideline structure that can inform future gender benchmarking tools. At the core of the framework is the question of how policy practices and implementation mechanisms can be more gender responsive in the context of women-led rural and farm innovation. The FLIARA Policy Benchmarking Guidelines offer:

- Guidelines for policymakers and other stakeholders to assist how they consider, plan and conduct policy benchmarking exercises in the context of policy to improve gender equality in rural and farm innovation and entrepreneurship. The guidelines aim to build understanding of benchmarking, what it exactly is and how it can be approached (Section 2).
- A tool for policy benchmarking, centered around a comprehensive yet flexible framework that can be used as a whole or focusing on specific themes (Section 3, Annex 1 and 2).
- Recommendations for the future are provided. Policy benchmarking is understudied and drawing out recommendations for the future is a key part of this report's results and the guidelines it offers (Section 4).
- A range of examples of policy measures and wider strategies are also highlighted. These in themselves offer a set of practices as examples for policymakers and other stakeholders, to shape their work on policy to better support women-led innovation in rural areas and farming (Annex 1).
- The results of multi-actor policy workshops carried out as part of FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP) events in Italy and Sweden are also reported here. The results inform the guidelines provided in this report, as well as more broadly provide rich insights on specific areas of policy improvement identified by the FLIARA project (Annex 3).

2. POLICY BENCHMARKING: WHAT, WHY AND WHEN

Benchmarking is a tool applied in different domains, such as benchmarking companies, places and policies. Benchmarking as a tool for policy improvement in a gender equality context can learn and draw lessons from the application of benchmarking in other domains. This section draws together important lessons to provide guidelines for benchmarking practice.

2.1 WHAT IS POLICY BENCHMARKING?

In essence, policy benchmarking is a comparative policy assessment tool that assesses policies in different contexts to identify broad learnings and more specific key lessons to improve policy. It involves systematic comparison of policies in different contexts (Fagerberg, 2001; 2003). Fundamentally, policy benchmarking has been described as “a structured approach to comparison to facilitate learning” (Papaioannou et al. 2006, p.93). Benchmarking is clearly also a distinct approach when compared to other methods of policy assessment. For example:

- Benchmarking is quite distinct from gender proofing that is: “A check carried out on any policy proposal to ensure that any potential gender discriminatory effect arising from that policy have been avoided and that gender equality is promoted” (EC, 1998, p.31).
- Benchmarking is also distinct from Gender Impact Assessment which is another method that can be used to conduct gender-related policy assessment and can be defined as: “Examining policy proposals to see whether they will affect women and men differently, with a view to adapting these proposals to make sure that discriminatory effects are neutralised and that gender equality is promoted” (EC, 1998, p.29).

Different methods of policy assessment can play a role at different points in the policy process. For example, Gender Impact Assessments can be carried out on policy proposals but also used to assess policy impacts post implementation. Benchmarking can be used to identify gaps to inform policy at the design stage, for example.

Benchmarking encompasses policy assessment by assessing policies against defined criteria. The chosen criteria underpin the framework that benchmarking is carried out within. For example:

- Benchmarking should be carried out within a framework of defined parameters. For example, to implement innovation policy benchmarking it is necessary to benchmark within a defined innovation policy framework. This framework must be built considering a specific rationale, such as the concept of innovation systems, as well as having a set of indicators to benchmark within this framework (García Manjón, 2010).

- Indicators are also centrally important because benchmarking comparisons involve: “The establishment of criterion, standard or reference point against which to establish targets and measure progress” (EC, 1998, p.13). In a wider benchmarking context, the measurement construct ‘indicators’ is often used which can be explained as: “...quantitative or qualitative tools which can be applied to measure performance or to identify good practices of organizations” (Papaioannou et al., 2006, p.93).

While we can define the core of policy benchmarking and identify some key characteristics, in practice, as a policy assessment tool, there is no standard accepted definition of benchmarking. There are also different approaches to how policy benchmarking is carried out (Arrowsmith et al. 2004). Two broad approaches to policy benchmarking can be identified: qualitative policy benchmarking and performance policy benchmarking. In practice, they can be combined in benchmarking exercises, while they can also be used separately (Dominique et al. 2013).

- The broad approach of qualitative policy benchmarking is where “Policy benchmarks seek to compare different countries’ policies in the same domain. These comparisons tend to be qualitative” (Dominique et al. 2013, p.506).
- The second quantitative approach can be classed as performance policy benchmarking that generate rankings or league table type results and “typically measure outcomes in the form of quantitative metrics” (Dominique et al. 2013, p.506).

2.2 APPROACHES TO POLICY BENCHMARKING

QUALITATIVE POLICY BENCHMARKING

In terms of methods to gather information, there are examples in gender equality contexts where a mostly qualitative survey is used to gather information on the existing state of play to understand and determine where the current policy benchmark is. Qualitative assessments of policies can also be an effective way of benchmarking policies around a set of specific domains of assessment that structure the survey and provide the framework for comparison, while also providing supporting information. These methods occupy a middle ground, moving away from the essence of benchmarking, which is comparison based on specific defined criteria, and toward a more insightful method of benchmarking. The results share the wider benefits of qualitative approaches to research, yielding rich detail and context embedded insights. For example, the GENDER ACTION project’s benchmarking and assessment survey collects information on existing policies and measures that integrate the gender dimension into the content of research, innovation and teaching, assessing 21 countries. The results then are used to identify promising practices and make wider recommendations (Rogg Korsvik et al. 2023).

Policy benchmarking surveys can also take the approach of using closed assessment questions to gain insights. Ruest-Archambault (2008) benchmark policy measures for

gender equality in science by examining whether they are either present, partially present or absent. Examples of measures included are the presence of equal opportunities laws in the country and a commitment to gender mainstreaming. Ruest-Archambault (2008) also note a limitation of this approach is that no distinction is made regarding the extent of implementation, for example if it is a newly applied policy measure or one that has been in place for decades.

A wider range of challenges facing qualitative benchmarking are discussed in Section 2.3 below.

PERFORMANCE POLICY BENCHMARKING

Performance-oriented benchmarking examples can be identified in rural contexts using quantitative data to compare different places against each other, with specific goals such as measuring levels of regional competitiveness. Take for example Simms et al. (2014) benchmarking of rural regions strengths and weaknesses to support community-based economic development. Another example is benchmarking of shrinking rural regions around the concept of smart shrinkage by Makkonen and Inkinen (2023).

Benchmarking can present its results as indices. While not called benchmarking as such, European level gender equality indices monitor regional gender equality using 33 indicators to build the female achievement index (FemAI) and the female disadvantage index (FemDI) (D'Ambrogio, 2023). If these types of indices could be replicated in the context of gender equality and women-led rural and farm innovation they could complement qualitative policy benchmarking.

However, the specific activity of performance-oriented policy benchmarking in a gender equality context based on comparing statistical indicators faces a range of challenges that are discussed next.

Criteria to measure and what data signifies

If including statistical indicators in benchmarking exercises, such as number of women-led enterprises, start-ups and self-employed at national or regional levels, these figures are not just impacted by policies. Changes in particular statistical measures could link to policy changes, but also the wider socio-economic context needs to be taken into account (Ruest-Archambault, 2008). There is no direct link between these desirable performance metrics and policy outcomes (Dominique et al. 2013). This is an important distinction to make in benchmarking that uses quantitative methods and measures. It is also relevant to be aware of what these measures tell us. Dominique et al. (2013, p.506) argue that quantitative methods are: "...often used to single out 'best in class' performers that could be the source of positive inspiration, as well as laggards, which might serve as cautionary tales".

Data availability and comparability

This is a broader issue impacting research relating to women-led rural and farm innovation and understanding of the role of women in rural areas, innovation and farming (e.g. as highlighted by for example Franić and Kovačićek 2019; ECA, 2021; EU CAP Network, 2022; Murtagh et al. 2024b). Data availability and comparability also impact the feasibility and operationalisation of quantitative performance policy benchmarking (Dominique et al. 2013). The EC (2003) enterprise policy scoreboard uses a series of statistical data as measures to assess the environment for enterprise. It is noted that its benchmarking is ultimately limited by data availability as well as the fact that using set criteria as indicators by its very nature assesses specific selected areas. Its core purpose is described as a way to: “monitor and provide evidence of recent developments” (EC, 2003, p.13). In the context of the EC (2003) benchmarking enterprise policy scoreboard it is noted that there is a temptation to include greater numbers of indicators in updated versions as data becomes available. However, just because certain data is available does not necessarily merit its inclusion in benchmarking. The key point is what the indicator signifies and the insights it provides. Data generated through EU policy monitoring systems, such as the the European Commission’s Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (PMEF) for the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), could also provide comparable datasets to potentially feed into quantitative performance policy benchmarking of particular policies.

Complex systems

Benchmarking is challenging in a context where there are highly complex and interconnected issues. The ModernAKIS project has applied benchmarking as a tool to assess Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) performance and notes challenges of benchmarking in this context because AKIS is not one entity or organisation but a system of networks where people, organisations and institutions share knowledge. There is also the issue of the heterogeneity of agricultural data and contexts that are part of AKIS (Giacopelli et al. 2025). Similarly, not only are gender equality issues in the context of innovation in farming and rural areas significantly complex, so are the policy systems influencing the innovation ecosystem. For example, the FLIARA Conceptual Framework has six perspectives (gender, rural, resilience, sustainability, innovation, policy and governance) embedded within it. It argues that women-led innovation needs to be understood as a phenomenon that occurs within an innovation ecosystem and women-led innovation journeys can be enabled by this system that includes: “resources, actors, governance, and support for female innovators that are located at different levels including individual, family, farm, community, rural region, state, and EU. Rural innovation ecosystems are embedded within gender relations, roles, stereotypes, and constructs that diverge across societies and cultures” (Farrell et al. 2023, p.9).

Applying scoring and weightings

If a scoring system is built into a benchmarking framework, where the countries compared end up with a summative score based on their performance against

benchmarks, then consideration of how scoring is achieved is important. Applying weightings is described by Dominique et al. (2013) as problematic because it embeds preferences for weighting certain indicators more or less heavily. A benchmarking framework with a scoring system must consider whether all benchmarked themes are equally important. For example, in the WBA's Gender Benchmarking Methodology, five of the six themes are similarly weighted to ensure the framework is balanced. However, governance and strategy are given the highest weighting to reflect the stakeholders' priorities (WBA, 2024). Framework themes (and potentially sub-themes, as relevant) need specific indicators that can be used to measure performance. Some themes may have only a few, while others require a large range of indicators. For example, WBA's Gender Benchmarking Methodology includes a total of 31 indicators across all its measurement areas, and these are equally weighted. Take governance and strategy as an example - one sub-theme is strategic action which has two measures attached to it while gender targets have four.

CHOOSING A BENCHMARKING METHOD

Different methods of benchmarking have different strengths and limitations. Using quantitative measures facilitate comparisons across time, while benchmarking using qualitative questionnaires that yield richer information can be more difficult to compare across time. Qualitative policy benchmarking will often yield richness and detailed results. The transferable actions for practice may be hard to identify among the results. Actionable results may need to be drawn out from the findings. One of the benefits described by Arrowsmith et al. (2004) of benchmarking in a corporate context is that ability to gain insights based on comparison and identify targets for action without the cloudiness of large amounts of detail found in the detailed reports that qualitative policy benchmarking can yield. In the context of benchmarking of AKIS, it is observed that hybrid approaches that combine quantitative indicators and qualitative observations help balance the challenges of both approaches (Giacopelli et al. 2025).

The method applied should be chosen with an awareness of the type of results that are desired. If an assessment that gives a clear high-level assessment is the goal, then benchmarking using closed questions or quantitative indicators is the approach that offers these results. If more insight, understanding and detail is the aim, then a qualitative questionnaire that unpacks context, details of policy measures and nuances is called for. We draw together some of the broad qualities of each approach in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Comparing Approaches to Policy Benchmarking

Benchmarking	Qualitative Policy	Performance Policy
Helps to:	Benchmarking	Benchmarking
Gather information	Gather broad and more detailed information on the existing state of development of policy in relation to a particular issue.	Gather specific and narrow information to make comparisons across time based on specific quantifiable criteria.
Gain context embedded insights	Gain context embedded insights on the presence or absence of particular policy practices.	Understand if particular policy practices or quantifiable policy impact criteria are present or absent in a particular context.
Identify policy practices	Identify promising policy practices for potential further assessment for their transferability or adaptation to new contexts.	Understand broadly if particular policy practices exist in a particular context that could then be subject to further research.
Identify recommendations for policy	Scope for policy recommendations based on the comparative analysis of qualitative insights.	Scope for policy recommendations based on comparative analysis of quantifiable criteria.

FIRST STEPS IN FLIARA BENCHMARKING ACTIVITIES

As part of FLIARA’s first steps to explore policy benchmarking an assessment of rural and farming policy and legal frameworks in relation to women-led Innovation was carried out in ten countries (Finland, Romania, Germany, Ireland, Slovenia, Italy, Sweden, Czech Republic, The Netherlands and Spain). A questionnaire including a series of closed questions and text responses formed the main assessment approach. This exercise was two-fold – to gain insight into the existing policy situation and to begin to explore potential ways to benchmark policy. In the emerging report titled D1.3: Assessment of Rural and Farming Policy and Legal Frameworks in relation to Women-led Innovation (Murtagh et al. 2024a), we chose to draw on the closed question responses in correlation with the contextual information that was provided. This assessment approach also included an inventory of the policies and laws identified in the questionnaire that were classified based on how they broadly interacted with the principles of the EU Gender Equality Strategy. Rather than providing a benchmarking assessment, this approach helped to categorise the policies and laws to understand the broad policy principles underpinning them and fed into our wider results presented in Murtagh et al. (2024a). These exercises allowed FLIARA to explore how to potentially combine qualitative assessment with more quantitative ones, but also understand there is much scope of further work in this area.

These reflections echo the observations of Papaioannou et al. (2006, p.96) who argue “broad-brush measures can help show where there are differences and this can aid

learning and the flow of new ideas about how to enhance performance through adoption of new or improved practices”. Broad performance measures used in qualitative benchmarking can generally aid learning and idea generation, while it is potentially the design of suitable and more specific performance measures that can lead benchmarking to offer tailored insights for policy. This challenge has informed our thinking in developing our proposed framework outlined in Section 3 below.

Further to this, what also clearly emerged from our first steps into exploring benchmarking is that to arrive at such definitive assessments a very comprehensive assessment of policy is needed. This speaks to the need for bottom-up approaches to policy benchmarking where policymakers are actively involved. These considerations link us to our next discussion and the wider challenges to reconcile in policy benchmarking.

2.3 WIDER CHALLENGES TO RECONCILE IN POLICY BENCHMARKING

Benchmarking policy has some wider shortcomings and challenges to reconcile. A range of broader challenges can be identified from research in the general field of policy benchmarking. They provide important insights that are discussed in this section. Our assessment focuses on these issues in the context of qualitative policy benchmarking which is the focus of the approach to benchmarking in the FLIARA project. These issues are not highlighted here to represent reasons not to do benchmarking. However, they are important to have awareness of and sometimes take very directly into account when designing benchmarking tools and building on the results they generate. These considerations generate challenges to reconcile and be clear about the position of a benchmarking approach in relation to them.

Conundrum 1: To effectively compare, must we compare like with like? Policy benchmarking needs to be compared based on similarities, but also compare with an awareness of core differences?

Benchmarking comparisons where there is a certain level of homogeneity make for a more straightforward exercise. Comparing at EU level does not often compare like with like. However, that said, EU contexts share some policy frameworks, such as the CAP, meaning there is a level of common ground when it comes to more specific policy areas. The FLIARA Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking (Murtagh et al. 2024b) discussed how different governance structures present challenges for cross-national benchmarking. For example, the Federal State system in Germany, and the large degree of autonomy that Federal States have in policy implementation, made assessing the full German context too layered for the scope of FLIARA. Another issue that leaves some EU states difficult to compare from a benchmarking perspective is overarching equality

laws, such as the Act on Equality between Women and Men in Finland. All other policies and legislation must follow this Act that includes the requirement for equal treatment, meaning that unless specific circumstances call for it, targeted measures to support women are not permitted under the legislation (Murtagh et al. 2024a, 2024b).

The notion of a certain level of similarity is important in policy benchmarking and deciding what the criteria are is important when benchmarking policy across institutional contexts. For example, Papaioannou et al. (2006, p.97) argue “Policy benchmarking involves comparisons...across different institutional contexts...It might be suggested that in policy benchmarking comparability depends on...socioeconomic, political and above all, institutional similarities of public sectors...for example, [comparing] a small country such as Slovakia, with historically distinct socio-economic, political and institutional developments against Canada, may find that there is too big gap in performance and practice of policy organizations — benchmarking fails to enhance interactive learning”.

This issue of comparability is also linked to our next point around the importance of context. Rather than the approach of identifying top performers, a context-sensitive approach is called for where it is argued for example: “...comparison with countries with similar characteristics or context could provide a more appropriate lens through which to view policy challenges” (Dominique et al. 2013, p.507).

Conundrum 2: Does context always matter? *Context matters to the lessons that can be learned and their transferability, but how much, when and how?*

Benchmarking’s transfer from the corporate world and its application in more complex contexts, such as comparing different places, needs to recognise and find ways to deal with the place-based complexities that impact comparison (Navarro et al., 2013). As already mentioned above, the issue is not just different policy frameworks, but the wider social, cultural and economic environment that these policies are implemented within (Papaioannou et al. 2006; Dominique et al., 2013). The core problem is how comparing different contexts can generate transferable policy lessons. Dominique et al. (2013, p.506) for example outline: “...the diversity of policy contexts as well as the importance of the enabling environment in influencing the outcomes of policies clearly constrains the transferability of policy lessons”. The importance of context is also clear from the CoP workshop findings. In a number of the workshop discussions the results emphasise the need for local co-creation and governance of policy (Annex 3).

For qualitative approaches that resist summative scoring and identifying top performers, recognising and working to reconcile this conundrum can perhaps become part of the strengths of benchmarking. But this cannot happen simply by doing a benchmarking exercise and publication of the results. A collaborative learning process appears crucial. This process should enable stakeholders to assess the transferability of the lessons learned and what needs to happen to act on them. This could include new policy design

or further information gathering that might include a specific detailed policy case study or gender impact assessment. This is the space where decisions can be made on the importance of context issues and how to deal with them. Dominique et al. (2013, p.511) for example accurately describe it: "...while policymakers often endorse the principle of learning by comparing, in reality, many consider their national circumstances to be too exceptional". This leads us to our next conundrum: "discussion about comparability and interactive learning also raises the question of who carries out the benchmarking" (Papaioannou, et al. 2006, p.101).

Conundrum 3: The policymaker role? *The process of benchmarking and the results it generates need policymaker co-creation?*

It is important there is an interest, willingness and capacity among policymakers to learn from the results of benchmarking to improve policy (Dominique et al. 2013; Kaiser and Prange, 2004). The comments of Dominique et al. (2013, p.506-7) highlight how this is not necessarily a black and white issue that can be taken for granted: "The use of international benchmarking to inform domestic policy also relies on a rather optimistic view regarding the motivations of policymakers, implying that they are performance-driven and seek continual improvement. It also suggests that policymakers are receptive to mutual learning processes". Based on recommendations made in the context of innovation policy, one potential way forward is the existence of a multi-actor platform, involving not just policymakers but other actors such as entrepreneurs themselves: "...an institutional platform for policy learning and policy transfer which comprises all relevant actors on a voluntary basis" (Kaiser and Prange, 2004, p.262).

Broadly speaking, two approaches to who does benchmarking are described in existing research. A bottom-up approach to benchmarking involves organisations that design and implement policies to also carry out benchmarking. A top-down approach broadly implies that benchmarking and the performance measures are used as an exercise external to these direct policymaking organisations (Papaioannou, et al. 2006). The value of collaborative benchmarking is noted (Papaioannou et al. 2006, Papaioannou 2007, Paasi 2005). The strength of this approach should help to at least start to address issues of comparability and transferability of benchmarking learnings. Papaioannou, et al. (2006, p.101) argue for example: "...the possibility of taking correct methodological decisions (which result in interactive learning) increases in the bottom-up/voluntary approach. This approach involves policymakers and stakeholders in all stages of the benchmarking process. Therefore, policymakers and stakeholders decide on comparability issues and learn good practices through voluntary interaction". The importance of stakeholder involvement in policy processes is also clear from the CoP workshop findings. The results include pointing to the need for local stakeholder shaping of policy design and decision-making (Annex 3).

Looking beyond providing spaces for policy learning and more closely at the process of bottom-up benchmarking, we must also recognise that policymakers also work within specific institutional and governance structures. The question of capacity also comes into this debate and the need for dedicated resources towards benchmarking. It does not appear to be a process that can just happen without resources. An example identified in our Initial Benchmarking Report (Murtagh et al 2024a) is worth reiterating here. Benchmarking can be a significant activity also that happens over a period of time. A phased, iterative approach can be illustrated by the Working Group for the Initiative on Women in Science and Engineering Institutional Report Card. It benchmarked efforts to support greater gender equality in STEM disciplines. Data was collected to establish the benchmark in its four-year pilot phase. The follow-on recognition phase worked to highlight high performers and motivate institutional changes (Beeler et al. 2019).

Conundrum 4: What benchmarking framework? *The criteria used to benchmark, be it a set of principles for qualitative benchmarking or numerical indicators, is a critical part of benchmarking. But how is the framework decided?*

A crucial part of benchmarking is the criteria or performance measures against which comparisons are made. One fundamental aspect of benchmarking is the principle of measurement and involves the selection of indicators for measurement of performance (Papaioannou et al., 2006). While in a corporate context, the WBA's Gender Benchmarking Methodology provides an example of a flexible, multi-dimensional framework that is used to assess companies on gender equality. It can be applied in full or part. The assessment covers six areas that tackle different aspects of what impacts gender inequality (Governance and strategy; representation; compensation and benefits; health and well-being; violence and harassment; marketplace and community). The WBA uses the framework to assess companies in 40 industries to achieve scale, while its full methodology is applied in two sectors where 100 companies are assessed in more depth (WBA, 2024).

However, building a benchmarking framework that allows for effective benchmarking outcomes is methodologically challenging. Observations made in the wider context of benchmarking innovation policy ring true in the context of benchmarking policy relating to gender equality, women-led rural and farm innovation. García Manjón (2010, p.14) argues: "The development of benchmarking analysis for innovation policies faces two major inconveniences: the lack of accepted innovation policy frameworks and the existence of suitable indicators to measure their performance". Changing social, cultural and economic conditions also creates new challenges for policy and calls for new and adapted policies. A benchmarking framework built today will likely need to be updated in time. For example, the third edition of EC (2003) enterprise policy scoreboard included sustainability as a new aspect of its benchmarking assessment and replaced some data indicators with others deemed to be better measures of specific issues.

Conundrum 5: Identifying practice or best practice? *The idea of best practice can be problematic because context matters. Rather should the goal be broader and what can new contexts learn from the example of others?*

Benchmarking in a corporate context can be used to identify best practices for implementation or adaptation in new contexts to improve performance (Anand and Kodali, 2008). However, in policy benchmarking best practice is a complex concept and its use needs careful consideration. There is also a question over whether the existing state of progress is best practice in terms of representing the ideal approach and desired situation. It could be better understood as the current best practice in terms of a leading example. In our report D1.5 Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking (Murtagh et al. 2024b), for example, it was identified how in the benchmarking of gender equality action plans, one approach by the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) positions benchmarks as not the desired situation but the current state of performance. Rather, targets are included to represent the desired situation (see EIGE, 2024). Defining and identifying what is best practice is a complex task and the notion that there is a universal best practice has limitations. For example, country contexts are heterogeneous presenting, for example, different laws, regulations, economies and cultures (Arrowsmith et al. 2004). The CoP workshop findings also help to illustrate this issue. One discussion focused on how policy can support work-family balance and pointed to how Sweden's model of parental leave represents a leading policy practice, however culture and context are also discussed to impact the transferability of such a policy model (Annex 3).

The term 'good practice' is also used to describe actions of different kinds that generate positive results and improvements, as well as hold potential for adoption or adaptation to other contexts (Lai, 2018). In a policy context, good practice can mean policy actions, such as the presence of particular policy measures, goals and actions in wider policy programmes and strategies. However, good practice implies an understanding of the positive results and improvements generated. Another way of thinking is the idea of 'promising practice'. These are actions that show some positive results or more broadly show promise to generate positive results. It is through assessment that it becomes understood if promising practice's implementation is good practice, as demonstrated by the approach of the RURALIZATION project (Murtagh et al. 2021).

2.4 WHY DO POLICY BENCHMARKING?

Clearly from the discussion so far, the quality of the outcomes that benchmarking offers depends on how it is designed and practiced. While there are many challenges to consider when benchmarking policy, it is also important to look beyond this and come back to the core principles of benchmarking to explore, when it is done well, what exactly does policy benchmarking offer as a policy learning tool? In this section we explore aspects of benchmarking that characterise this approach and hence become part of the core offering of benchmarking as a policy tool.

There are broad and specific roles that benchmarking can play in policy improvement. Broadly speaking, it can act as “...an evaluative tool, well-constructed international benchmarks may provide a useful point of reference to situate and assess a country’s relative standing in a particular policy area” (Dominique et al. 2013, p.510). Some more specific uses of benchmarking are next explored. However, these benefits are tied in particular to overcoming limitations outlined in the conundrums discussed in Section 2.3 above.

WHAT POLICY BENCHMARKING OFFERS

Learning by comparison to gain ideas for improvement

Benchmarking policy can be used to identify the existence of particular policy measures in national contexts. Part of how Ruest-Archambault (2008) benchmark policy measures for gender equality in science is by assessing the presence of particular measures by comparing different country contexts. If policy benchmarking is not an isolated exercise and is carried out across time it can monitor and compare changes in the existence of particular policy measures. For example, the EC (2003) enterprise policy scoreboard provides a third edition of this benchmarking exercise aiming to monitor enterprise policy developments at EU and Member State level and assess policy advancements. What it offers is: “Instead of simply pointing out the gaps in performance, benchmarking allows exploration of a focused set of practices to enable better performance” (Papaioannou, et al. 2006, p.92). Learning by comparison that is at the core of benchmarking provides insights for policy improvement. It provides a specific insight compared to other methods of policy assessment. For example, Giacobelli et al. (2025, p.11) argue: “...evaluation answers to questions such as “what has happened?” or “what is happening?”, benchmarking addresses the question “what can be improved?”. It does not therefore provide ready-made solutions that can simply be transferred from one context to another (Dominique et al. 2013).

One of the questions raised in the benchmarking literature is “how learning takes place in benchmarking” (Papaioannou et al. 2006, p.94). For example, learning from the context of food and health policy, Swinburn et al. (2013) construct a monitoring framework for government policy and action that also includes a benchmarking component. A series of policy domains are at the core of the framework. However, this multi-layered framework is then made up of a general good practice description for each domain and a series of more specific good practice statements. In the future, following further testing and refinement, it is argued this framework could become an EU policy index with weighting attached to different domains and indicators assigned scores (Swinburn et al. 2013).

Focused assessment within a defined framework

Benchmarking policy in the context of gender equality, women-led rural and farm innovation faces the challenge of the framework to benchmark within, the rationale

underpinning it and indicators to use to assess performance. However, this can also be seen as a strength of benchmarking: it provides a clear structure to assess policy. Benchmarking frameworks might include benchmarking against particular policy strategies and their specific goals and ambitions. Whether a well-worked framework or a wider framework for comparison is used, this also means that benchmarking embeds normative views. It is important that benchmarking is done with a clear awareness of the importance of the benchmarking framework as well as the fact that this embeds a way of thinking. For example, Papaioannou et al. (2006, p.92) argue: "...its potential value to managers and increasingly to public policymakers has been that it offers a normative framework around which one can construct a development agenda".

Learning from promising practice

The idea of a promising practice, where it is understood that the policy actions either show some positive results or show promise to generate positive results, is a useful learning outlook for policy benchmarking. Promising practices may then need further exploration for real policy learning. It can start with benchmarking, however, it potentially needs to be accompanied by supporting qualitative research so that transfer is effective. In an innovation policy context, similar issues are raised by Kaiser and Prange (2004), who argue policy learning and transfer should be well-informed and consider national characteristics, such as norms, values and economic characteristics as well as governance issues such as institutional structures. It is potentially through other deeper and more focused methods of policy assessment that the label of good practice and best practice can be applied. The promising practice concept then appears more appropriate to use in a policy benchmarking context that does not evaluate measures, it identifies those that appear promising. The concept is clearer about its purpose in terms of providing ideas for new or adapted approaches and fits better with the idea of benchmarking as a learning tool.

Table 2: Policy Benchmarking and Learnings from Promising Practices

Benchmarking	Explanation
Offers:	
Examples of policy to replicate	This could involve copying policy measures, methods of implementation or wider policy plans that exist in another context and fit well with the new context of application.
Examples of policy to adapt	Learning from policy measures, methods of implementation or wider policy plans that adapt examples and will often include changes to adapt to the new context.
Different aspects of policy to replicate and/or adapt	This can take different aspects of policy measures, methods of implementation or wider policy plans and implement a hybrid new approach that constructs a new approach from various aspects of policies
Wider learnings and inspiration	External policy standards provide comparisons and help identify potential policy gaps and actions that provide insights to inform learning and improvements more widely.

Source: Author elaboration informed by Dominique et al. (2013) and Kaiser and Prange (2004).

BOUNDARIES OF POLICY BENCHMARKING

Benchmarking also provides one part of a story and takes a specific perspective within it. There are many potential parts that can make up the whole story that needs to be accounted for when seeking to improve policy. Discussing benchmarking limitations, it is also noted that the results should be interpreted with care and taken in the context of all available evidence analysing policy to shape improvements in future policy design and implementation (DG For Research and Innovation, 2002). This raises the question of what are the boundaries of international comparative policy benchmarking? This also depends on the specific approach to benchmarking and exceptions may arise, but some general aspects are outlined below to help stakeholders and policymakers evaluate if benchmarking is indeed the right tool for the goals they want to achieve.

Evaluative assessment of policy performance

Benchmarking does not explain why and how a policy worked, such as the causal relationships that are behind the success of a particular policy measure. Dominique et al. (2013, p.508) explain: "...neither performance nor policy benchmarks typically capture the complexity of the process and the dynamics of policy design and implementation". On the other hand, evaluation focuses on gaining a more comprehensive understanding of policy performance while benchmarking embeds policy assessment and learning by comparison at its core. Giacomelli et al. (2025, p.10-11) argue for example: "One main distinction between benchmarking and evaluation lies in their underlying purpose or intent. Evaluation is primarily oriented towards accountability and carries an inherently judgmental character...Benchmarking, by contrast, is centered on learning...and opportunities for improvement through comparison and reflection". Benchmarking

provides broad evidence on policies. For example, in the FLIARA assessment of policy to support our benchmarking work the project carried out desk-based analysis of policy documents and reports (Murtagh et al. 2024a). It is perhaps the task of other methods of policy assessment to address what Dominique et al. (2013, p.507) describe: "...benchmarks often fail to capture the evolution of policies and performance over time to take into account different starting points and to focus on how countries transition and advance from one level of development to the next". CoP workshop findings also reinforce this idea. Some of the discussions for example focused on the existing policy support system and the need for simplification, such as reducing bureaucracy, the need for more flexibility in assessment criteria and better information provision to potential beneficiaries (Annex 3). Deeper evaluative assessments of specific policies are needed to capture the specific issues creating more systemic barriers in the policy support system.

Learning from policy failures and local experimentation

Other important ways to inform policy improvement are learning from what did not work well, local knowledge and novel policy approaches that seek to test new approaches. If too great an emphasis is placed on comparative benchmarking such modes of learning could be overshadowed, as argued by Dominique et al. (2013): "These modalities, being contextually embedded, can contribute just as significantly to knowledge for policymaking ...homegrown initiatives can be equally, if not even more powerful, sources of learning...local experimentation is informative in building appropriate policies that best match the needs and capacities of communities" (Dominique et al. 2013, p.511).

Impact of civil society

In our assessment of policy and law, and the wider policy environment for women-led innovation, in relation to networks the importance of civil society organisations such as women's and farming organisations emerged in national contexts (Murtagh et al. 2024a). A policy framework can facilitate a strong civil society however the dynamics of civil society are more complex than what a benchmarking framework can capture in the context of assessing policies in relation to gender equality and women-led rural and farm innovation.

3. BUILDING A BENCHMARKING FRAMEWORK

3.1 BUILDING THE FLIARA BENCHMARKING FRAMEWORK

The FLIARA project took an incremental, phased approach towards the end goal of developing guidelines for policy benchmarking. As part of the guidelines, FLIARA has also tackled the complex task of proposing a framework that the whole policy system interacts with that is relevant to women-led rural and farm innovation. The data FLIARA worked to incorporate, and which informs the framework, is illustrated in Figure 1. The framework is built on the analysis of ten EU countries: Finland, Romania, Germany, Ireland, Slovenia, Italy, Sweden, Czech Republic, The Netherlands and Spain. The specific steps taken are outlined below.

Figure 1: Data Informing the FLIARA Benchmarking Framework

Step 1: Planning and current policy assessment: Define the scope of the initial policy assessment, policy data collection and analysis.

- Define the scope of the benchmarking through analysis of the European Gender Equality Strategy, and other relevant strategies, to identify an initial guiding approach for policy benchmarking on its gender equality performance. A series of assessment principles were identified.
- Assess current policy and carry out data collection through a desk-based analysis (early/mid 2024). This focused on policy documents, wider reports and literature at national levels underpinned by the assessment principles through a qualitative questionnaire, including closed questions, as well compiling an Excel inventory of policies and laws (D1.3: Assessment of Rural and Farming Policy and Legal Frameworks in relation to Women-led Innovation, Murtagh et al. 2024a).

- Develop preliminary guidelines on policy benchmarking on gender equality performance in relation to women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. This focused on drawing out insights and broad learnings for policy benchmarking from the inventory and assessment of policy and legal frameworks. An initial light touch review of benchmarking literature was also carried out. This all led to the identification of a set of initial broad benchmark statements to act as potential reference points for good practice (D1.5: Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking, Murtagh et al., 2024b).

Step 2: Analysis of areas for policy improvement: Better understand the current situation in relation to the policy needs of women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.

- Explore policy needs through Benchmarking and Policy Design workshops held at FLIARA Community of Practice events (Galway, July 2024 and Slovenia, September 2024).
- Analysis of the 20 FLIARA case studies from the ten FLIARA partner countries using an assessment template based on the PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, Legal) framework to understand the key barriers and opportunities facing women-led innovation in farming and rural areas of relevance for policy.
- Draw together the above evidence and the outcomes of Step 1 in D4.3: Initial Benchmarking Report (Murtagh et al. 2024c) to begin to identify potential benchmarks for policy on its gender equality performance in relation to women-led rural and farm innovation.
- Based on the emerging results from D4.3, further explored more specific policy needs through Benchmarking and Policy Design workshops held at FLIARA Community of Practice events (Italy, January 2025 and Sweden, May 2025). For a summary of the wider results, see Annex 3.

Step 3: Build the benchmarking framework: Constructing guidelines and a proposed framework for benchmarking policy in relation to women-led rural and farm innovation.

- Review benchmarking literature to more deeply understand practical considerations in relation to benchmarking policy in the context of better supporting women-led innovation in rural and farming contexts.
- Building of an initial benchmarking framework through mapping of the targeted actions identified in D4.3 Initial Benchmarking Report against the set of initial broad benchmark statements from D1.5.
- Recalibration and refinement of the framework drawing together a range of FLIARA policy relevant evidence, the second set of T4.3 Benchmarking and Policy Design CoP Workshops and deeper analysis of the outcomes of T1.4 Assessment of Policy and Legal Frameworks to Support Policy Benchmarking in light of the outcomes of Step 2. The framework is also informed by the final key outcomes of WP2's Future's research (Kuhmonen and Tembo, 2024b) and the FLIARA Policy Briefs (Kang et al. eds. 2025). This resulted in arriving at a framework with five main themes, including sub-themes linked to each main theme.

Figure 2: FLIARA Tasks and Key Steps Towards the FLIARA Benchmarking Framework

3.2 THE FLIARA BENCHMARKING FRAMEWORK

The FLIARA Policy Benchmarking Framework provides a flexible framework designed to facilitate benchmarking of policy measures supporting women-led rural and farm innovation. Themes have direct and indirect influence on women-led innovation in these contexts. The framework structure is built drawing on the architecture used in other benchmarking contexts and is most notably informed by Short et al. (2013), Swinburn et al. (2013) and WBA (2024).

- The policy benchmarking framework has **five main themes**, each with a series of **sub-themes** (see Figure 3). The framework is designed in this way so it is flexible where one theme or potentially also a sub-theme within a particular dimension can be used to benchmark policy.
- Each theme and sub-theme are described and a short rationale for it is provided. Each theme and sub theme is then further detailed in dedicated tables. This is where a descriptive '**benchmarking principle**' is attached to each sub-theme. This is a statement of good practice that represents a broad ambition for where policy action should aim to be and embeds possibilities for policy improvement. This concept was introduced in the report D1.5: Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking (Murtagh et al., 2024b). This is where initial benchmark statements to act as potential reference points for good practice were proposed. This final set of benchmarking principles builds on this initial set of statements and presents the more refined idea of benchmarking principles.
- **Potential policy actions** that support the benchmarking principle are next outlined. The list of potential actions intends to be comprehensive, but not

exhaustive. The list of potential actions can be used as the basis for benchmarking exercises under that theme and sub-theme. Those outlined reflect a distillation of key insights emerging from the FLIARA project and can be used as the basis for a qualitative benchmarking exercise (as shown in benchmarking template questionnaire drafted in Annex 2, also see the next steps discussed in Section 3.3). However, in real world applications this list would also need review with potential actions added to reflect changed and wider circumstances than the scope of the FLIARA project can account for. This would be an important step in the comparative benchmarking learning process where actions are reviewed and agreed among the benchmarking team implementing the benchmarking exercise.

- **Examples** are provided and are intended to be illustrative (Annex 1). They are not intended to represent best practice or good practice. They can be interpreted as practices with promise. They include specific policy measures/schemes, wider policy programmes and methods of policy implementation to take account of gender equality issues. In some sections, we do not provide concrete, real world examples but provide wider ideas for future policies and possibilities for improvement.

Figure 3: The FLARA Benchmarking Framework

THEME 1: EQUAL ECONOMIC PARTICIPATION

What: Targeted actions to support women’s equal participation in farming, rural enterprise and innovation.

Rationale: Women-led rural and farm innovation needs to be supported to flourish through a diverse range of targeted supports that address women’s needs such as improved access to finance, networks, knowledge and skills development opportunities. Within the support system, specific needs should also be addressed, such as targeted supports for particular groups of women (e.g. marginalised or young women), place-based opportunities (e.g. remote or mountain areas), specific innovation opportunities (ecological, digital, social enterprise) or specific business-stage (set-up, expansion).

Table 3: Sub-Theme - 1.1 Access to Finance

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>A diverse targeted support system is in place to facilitate access to finance for women-led rural and/or farm enterprise and innovation. It is appropriate and designed in light of the distinct needs, challenges and characteristics of women-led rural and farm innovation. This support framework acts both as an incentive and support.</i></p>
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Existence of state-supported micro credit scheme that targets women or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation ✓ Existence of targeted grants exist that support the development of women-led innovation development or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation ✓ Existence of interest free or low-cost finance that targets women or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation ✓ Finance support programmes target specific stages of women-led innovation development or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation

Table 4: Sub-Theme - 1.2 Access to Networks

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>Networks are a central part of the enabling environment for women-led innovation. Policy actions directly support networking as well as indirectly support activities (e.g. organisations, projects) that provide spaces to network for women in rural and farm innovation.</i></p>
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Women-led rural and/or farm enterprise networking supports exist ✓ Support is available for networks and networking for women involved in innovation and entrepreneurship ✓ Support is available for organisations that enable networks and networking in rural areas and/or farming that target women and/or specific needs relevant to women-led innovation

Table 5: Sub-Theme - 1.3 Access to Education and Up-Skilling Opportunities

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>Innovation can demand a range of skills and capacities, such as business skills and more specialist expertise. Innovators also need to stay aligned with new knowledge and changing enterprise needs. The enabling environment for women-led innovation includes appropriate supports to build skills and innovation capacities supporting participation and success in women-led innovation.</i></p>
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Women-led rural and/or farm entrepreneurship training programme exists ✓ Targeted upskilling programmes supporting women-led rural and/or farm innovation and entrepreneurship that take a peer-to-peer learning approach exist ✓ Measures are in place to assist improved gender balance in agricultural training programmes and education ✓ Business and innovation training targets women in rural areas and/or farming and is designed with their specific needs in mind ✓ The wider knowledge and innovation system focuses on the needs of women involved in rural and/or farm innovation

Table 6: Sub-Theme - 1.4 Integrated and Wider Policies/Support Programmes

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>Programmes exist that support women’s equal participation in rural and/or farm innovation that combine different aspects of the sub-themes 1.1 to 1.3.</i></p>
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Targeted programmes exist to support women’s increased participation in the rural and/or farm economy ✓ There is a dedicated policy focus on rural and/or farm women’s economic empowerment through women-led innovation and entrepreneurship

THEME 2: EQUAL GOVERNANCE PARTICIPATION

What: Actions to support gender balance in governance spaces, representation and decision making. These actions may target rural and/or farm women directly, but wider measures targeting gender balance and more equal participation in governance spaces are also relevant.

Rationale: Women should be equally represented in the decision-making spaces of governance to facilitate their needs and views be taken into account. There should be adequate opportunities for women to influence the decisions that impact them. This applies to a variety of areas, such as politics, state agencies and wider organisations in

civil society. More balanced representation can also support improved decision-making and governance outcomes such as better policymaking.

Table 7: Sub-Theme - 2.1 Politics

Table 7: Sub-Theme - 2.1 Politics
<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>A range of measures exist to support gender balance in politics, tackling the issue directly (e.g. representation) and indirectly (stereotypes and norms).</i></p>
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Measures exist to support gender balance in elected representatives at different governance levels (e.g. local, regional, national) ✓ Measures exist to support the increased visibility of women in politics and civil society ✓ Measures exist to build women’s skills and capacities to become involved in politics

Table 8: Sub-Theme - 2.2 Governance Spaces

Table 8: Sub-Theme - 2.2 Governance Spaces
<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>Actions support women’s representation in wider governance spaces that influence policy processes, such as policy design and implementation, as well as governance process in organisations relevant to women-led rural and farm innovation.</i></p>
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Dedicated mechanisms are in place to facilitate rural and/or farm women’s issues are taken into account in policy ✓ Actions exist, such as quotas or targets, to increase gender balance in state governance spaces ✓ Actions exist, such as quotas or targets, to increase gender balance in other policy governance spaces ✓ Measures exist to support gender balance in stakeholder organisations and private companies

THEME 3: GENDER RELATED WORK-LIFE CONFLICTS, STEREOTYPES AND NORMS

What: Actions to support gender balance in caring responsibilities, support wider work-life balance challenges, particularly those specific to farming and rural enterprise professions, as well as wider actions to dispel traditional gender stereotypes and norms.

Rationale: Innovative policy measures need to work to address gender stereotypes, traditional gender norms and patriarchal attitudes. Measures need to tackle improving the visibility and recognition of existing rural and/or farm women-led innovation. Policies need to effectively address the challenge of balancing all of life’s demands, such as parental leave and enabling innovators to take holiday leave.

Table 9: Sub-Theme - 3.1 Work-Life Balance

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>A strong and stable support system is in place that supports work and family life balance. A strong and stable supports system is also in place that supports work and wider life balance, such as providing for leisure time.</i></p>
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Flexible and adequate parental leave exists that is paid, available to the self-employed and provides for sharing of leave among parents ✓ Low cost and high-quality childcare places are guaranteed ✓ A publicly funded support system exists supporting farmers to take time off (e.g. sick leave, pregnancy leave, parental leave)

Table 10: Sub-Theme - 3.2 Stereotypes and Norms

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>Policies address increasing the visibility of women-led innovation and challenge gender stereotypes related to work-life and professions.</i></p>
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Measures exist to support gender balance and address gender stereotypes and norms in rural economy sectors where women are under-represented ✓ Measures are in place to assist improving the visibility and recognition of existing women-led innovation in rural areas and farming ✓ Measures exist targeting emerging generations to impact a shift in traditional stereotypes and norms in relation to entrepreneurship, innovation and farming

THEME 4: GENDER RELATED POLICY AND LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

What: Actions dedicated to support gender equality through specific policies, laws and tools. These actions may target rural and/or farm women directly, but wider measures targeting gender equality are also relevant.

Rationale: The overarching gender equality policy and governance frameworks that exist at national levels influence the direction of policies impacting women-led rural and farm innovation. In our previous reports (D1.5 and D4.3) we have noted how a systematic approach to promoting gender equality is taken in countries such as Finland and

Sweden. This impacts the potential for policies that target women directly. This makes it important to look at gender equality with a more cross-cutting lens in this framework.

Table 11: Sub-Theme - 4.1 Gender Equality Laws, Policies and Tools

Table 11: Sub-Theme - 4.1 Gender Equality Laws, Policies and Tools
<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>National laws, policies and governance systems provide a strong overarching framework from the top-down that ensures gender equality issues are taken account of in rural, farm and innovation policy.</i></p>
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Gender mainstreaming is provided for in law and its practice is evident in rural, farm and innovation policy ✓ Gender mainstreaming is supported by a strong institutional framework to ensure its implementation ✓ Gender budgeting has a legal basis and is implemented following international good practice ✓ National gender equality policy devotes specific and adequate attention to the needs of rural and farm women

Table 12: Sub-Theme - 4.2 Gender Equality in Rural, Farm and Innovation Policy

Table 12: Sub-Theme - 4.2 Gender Equality in Rural, Farm and Innovation Policy
<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>Strong and diverse policy actions support gender equality through policy implementation or specific policy design. Policy implementation is done in a gender-sensitive way and is designed in mind of current inequalities faced by women in rural areas and farming.</i></p>
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Selection criteria to qualify for support measures place priority on support for women ✓ A gender perspective is built into rural, farm and innovation policy monitoring and evaluation ✓ Gender equality is an objective of rural, farm and innovation policies and includes mandatory minimum thresholds for implementation of this objective ✓ Existence of policies promoting a gender balance in access to land, especially for new generations.

THEME 5: RURAL SUSTAINABILITY

What: Actions to support the sustainability of rural areas and farms that also support an enabling environment for women-led rural and farm innovation.

Rationale: FLIARA evidence shows how women-led rural and farm innovation supports rural sustainability. Further tapping into the opportunities calls for policies to support rural

sustainability goals, such as unlocking the potential for social, cultural, environmental and digital innovation in rural areas and on farms.

Table 13: Sub-Theme - 5.1 Access to Resources

Benchmarking principle: <i>Policies support a strong enabling environment and access to resources to support improved rural and farm sustainability.</i>
Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle: <ul style="list-style-type: none">✓ Dedicated funding supports exist for innovation and entrepreneurship activities in areas where women-led innovation is more often found, such as agritourism, short food supply chains and the social economy✓ Dedicated funding supports exist for innovation and entrepreneurship activities in areas of future opportunity for women-led innovation such as digital and circular economies✓ Measures facilitate access to public land for sustainable farming and rural projects supporting sustainability✓ Public policy support is facilitated by intermediaries supporting information provision and navigating application processes

Table 14: Sub-Theme - 5.2 Co-Creation and Cooperation

Benchmarking principle: <i>Policies support a strong enabling environment facilitating co-creation and cooperation to support improved rural and farm sustainability.</i>
Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle: <ul style="list-style-type: none">✓ Dedicated supports exist to enable the formation of more collaborative organisational forms and membership based organisational models✓ A strong support framework is in place to support locally-led bottom-up development of the rural and/or farm economy✓ A strong support framework is in place to support multi-actor cooperation projects

Table 15: Sub-Theme - 5.3 Rural and Farm Regeneration

Benchmarking principle: <i>Policies support a strong enabling environment to enhance the sustainable regeneration of the rural population and economy.</i>
Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle: <ul style="list-style-type: none">✓ Strategies exist to support rural and/or farm development approaches that embed a double or triple bottom line (social, environmental and economic) in their outcomes✓ Strategies exist of relevance to rural areas and /or farming that focus on harnessing novel areas of under harnessed and future opportunity✓ Strategies exist to support rural and/or farm development approaches that support rural and farm generational renewal✓ Specific supports target rural return migration and entrepreneurship

3.3 NEXT STEPS FOR THE FRAMEWORK?

The FLIARA Policy Benchmarking Framework provides a model that can be applied to create qualitative benchmarking questionnaires to benchmark policy in the context of women-led rural and farm innovation. The most complete assessment would apply the full framework given the range of policies that impact women-led rural and farm innovation. FLIARA research has understood women-led innovation as occurring within an innovation ecosystem of for example resources, actors and governance systems. FLIARA also conceptualised women-led innovation as a journey that involves a set of distinct steps (Farrell et al. 2023). Benchmarking needs to avoid the tendency to look for a silver bullet. For example, Dominique et al. (2013, p.508) argue: “While their popularity has fostered a greater desire for credible information about the performance of public organizations and policies, it has also promoted a fixation on single measures of success and on more quantifiable aspects of performance”.

Annex 2 provides an example of a purely qualitative assessment questionnaire based on Theme 1 (Equal Economic Participation) of the FLIARA Benchmarking Framework. The other themes, sub-themes and policy actions outlined in the FLIARA Framework also lend themselves to this qualitative assessment questionnaire format and can be similarly applied to carry out a qualitative benchmarking assessment relating to these themes. This provides a provisional template for a policy benchmarking tool to identify gaps and areas for potential improvement in a specific context. With further work, the framework has potential to be adapted to inform future tools for policy benchmarking. In addition, before operationalising a benchmarking exercise using this specific provisional tool, a number of further recommendations are important:

- An initial review and piloting of the questionnaire is recommended to identify any areas for refinement in the questionnaire design. For example, the questionnaire currently includes only open-ended questions. Closed questions could also be

useful if those benchmarking would like to gather insights for at-a-glance comparisons across contexts. For example, the FLIARA assessment questionnaire used to gather evidence for our D1.3 policy assessment also included closed questions (see Annexes in Murtagh et al. 2024a). This does add to the complexity of the questionnaire and calls for rural, farming and wider targeted policies towards women to be assessed separately. Our conclusion from using closed questions in this questionnaire was also that these questions were at times hard to definitively answer and should be seen in context of the wider qualitative answers and not taken out of this context (Murtagh et al. 2024a).

- It would also be necessary to review the questionnaire for additional policy actions that could be deemed important to benchmark in that specific context.
- The benchmarking assessment questions are also relatively generic. More specific qualitative questions could be warranted in specific contexts. The questions currently included aim to capture:
 - Promising policy practices: Do these types of measure(s) exist? Do they work well and why?
 - Shortcomings in policy practices: If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?
 - Areas of unmet need: If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in the context?

4. CONCLUSION: POLICY BENCHMARKING RECOMMENDATIONS

In this report, FLIARA has explored both the promise and challenge of the wider use of policy benchmarking as a tool to improve policy in relation to women-led rural and farm innovation. Benchmarking as a tool used in policy contexts can integrate lessons from corporate contexts, however, transfer also needs to consider deeply the policy context itself. The FLIARA approach has been to work towards building on the strengths of benchmarking with a strong awareness of the limitations, as well the complex task at hand.

This report assessed current knowledge on policy benchmarking, and based on this, provides a set of general guidelines for consideration in relation to policy benchmarking. The report also develops a specific framework that provides a guideline structure intended to inform future gender benchmarking tools. Recommendations for further work and next steps to apply this potential are also provided. Finally, here we make some recommendations towards future research and policy benchmarking practice.

Better harness the value in the process as well as the results

Policy benchmarking as a bottom-up exercise, where those being benchmarked are carrying out the benchmarking, or are at least strongly involved in the process, becomes important. For the learning principle at the heart of benchmarking to activate, those who implement policies must value and make use of the results of benchmarking. A potential benefit of benchmarking comes from harnessing the value of this process as well as the results it generates. This approach calls for “regular interaction between those who monitor the targets and those who have to implement them” (Arrowsmith et al. 2004, p.325). If benchmarking can be harnessed as a tool for improvement of policy influencing women-led innovation in rural and farming contexts, there is a potential role here for policy evaluation units such as the European Evaluation Helpdesk for the CAP (EU CAP Network, no date). Combining benchmarking with detailed policy case studies on promising practices identified would also support better use of the results.

More multi-actor research is needed

Further research is needed on a number of different levels. We need to better understand what policymakers think of benchmarking, if there is appetite for this type of policy learning and how policymakers themselves assess the extent of the challenges and wider conundrums identified in this report. It is also argued that learning from the promising practices identified by benchmarking is not straightforward, and along with development of new policy, and this may also need institutional change (Paasi, 2005). There is also a need to explore further how to better combine the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative approaches to benchmarking, as well as embedding wider policy learning tools within the benchmarking process.

Explore benchmarking in specific policy frameworks

Promise also lies in focusing benchmarking on particular areas where there is common ground, such as shared EU policy frameworks like CAP or Cohesion Policy. The common ground should help, to some extent at least, manage the context issue. This approach should also provide a similar basis for comparisons and a clear boundary for what is benchmarked. This could also provide a testing ground for future development of benchmarking as a policy assessment tool.

Dedicated resources needed to support benchmarking

One overarching question that FLIARA posed in the first step of our benchmarking activities was if policy benchmarking could become a tool used to assist with gender mainstreaming and the range of policy assessment tools that support this process. Policy benchmarking has promise, but further research is needed, as well as resources to support policy benchmarking. The real promise potentially lies in benchmarking if it was to become an accepted, regular practice. Benchmarking would also need resources behind it and a system that ensures data collection, comparison, analysis, learning from results and updating of benchmarks. Benchmarking appears most effective when it emphasises learning from results alongside their generation.

ANNEX 1: BENCHMARKING FRAMEWORK WITH ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

Theme 1: Equal Economic Participation

Table A1. 1: Sub-Theme - 1.1 Access to Finance

Benchmarking principle:	
<p><i>A diverse targeted support system is in place to facilitate access to finance for women-led rural and/or farm enterprise and innovation. It is appropriate and designed in light of the distinct needs, challenges and characteristics of women-led rural and farm innovation. This support framework acts both as an incentive and support.</i></p>	
Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle	Illustrative examples
<p>Existence of state-supported micro credit scheme that targets women or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation</p>	<p>An example highlighted in Spain’s Policy Brief No. 1 would support this principle. The Business Support Programme for Women (PAEM), co-financed by the European Social Fund, provides microcredit of up to €30,000 without requiring third-party guarantees (see Kang et al. eds. 2025). Another example that targets a particular group of women from Italy is the ‘Microcredito di libertà’ or ‘Microcredit of freedom’ that provides for an interest-free loan of €50,000 maximum to start up or develop entrepreneurial initiatives and is designed for women assisted by Anti-Violence Centers or guests of Shelter Houses who would not have easy access to traditional bank credit (Sivini et al. 2024). The need for micro credit is also highlighted elsewhere more widely in the FLIARA project’s findings. The Italian rural case study assessment carried out for D4.3 for example outlines a new policy idea suggesting a micro credit scheme providing quick and easy access to limited amounts of funding (e.g. €20,000 - €40,000) for start-up and later developing innovations (Murtagh et al. 2024c).</p>
<p>Existence of targeted grants exist that support the development of women-led innovation development or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation</p>	<p>In Italy, the Innovative Mountain Women’s Enterprise scheme finances investment in women-led business projects with high technological and innovative content in mountain municipalities by providing a non-repayable grant for up to 70% of eligible expenses and to a maximum of €70,000. In Italy, the CAP 2023-2027 intervention on investments in agricultural holdings for diversification into non-agricultural activities supporting women’s enterprise is included as a priority (alongside young people) as part of the beneficiary selection criteria. Wider innovation supports managed by ISMEA can also be identified in Italy were the Innovation Fund that provides grants to support increased productivity through</p>

	digital and technological solutions and incentives for tourism enterprises that benefits agritourism. Higher grant rates are available for women’s enterprise (Sivini et al. 2024). In Ireland the CAP the On-Farm Capital Investment Scheme supports increased farm efficiency and competitiveness by providing financial support to farmers. Grants are provided to cover 40% of costs however women and young farmers can claim 60% of the costs (up to a maximum investment ceiling). (Murtagh et al. 2024d).
Existence of interest free or low-cost finance that targets women or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation	In Italy, the ISMEA scheme 'More Enterprise - Youth and Women Entrepreneurship in Agriculture' provides interest free finance to women (and young people) intending to take over a farm or have done so in the previous two years, providing support for business expansion and improving competitiveness (Sivini et al. 2024).
Finance support programmes target specific stages of women-led innovation development or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation	In Italy, Smart & Start Italia supports the creation and development of innovative start-ups financing projects between €100,000 and €1.5 million with interest-free, guaranteed financing that covers 80% of eligible expenses, but up to 90% for women only start-ups (Sivini et al. 2024). The CoP workshop results also support this policy action where one policy wish was that that there is better start-up and growth financial support for women entrepreneurs (Annex 3).

Table A1. 2: Sub-Theme - 1.2 Access to Networks

Benchmarking principle: <i>Networks are a central part of the enabling environment for women-led innovation. Policy actions directly support networking as well as indirectly support activities (e.g. organisations, projects) that provide spaces to network for women in rural and farm innovation.</i>	
Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle	Illustrative examples
Women-led rural and/or farm enterprise networking supports exist	In Ireland, the Women's Rural Entrepreneurial Network targets self-employed women, start-up or established women entrepreneurs. It is a local scheme run by LAGs in county Cork and Limerick. Also in Ireland, depending on local needs, it is stated in Ireland’s CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027 that women-only knowledge transfer groups can be set up (Murtagh et al. 2024a). However, case study evidence highlighted in Ireland’s Policy Brief No. 5 identified concern among women relating to such groups if

	<p>their effects included to segregate women, creating divides among different genders in farming (see Kang et al. eds. 2025).</p>
<p>Support is available for networks and networking for women involved in innovation and entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Women involved in rural and farm innovation can benefit from wider women’s enterprise and innovation networks. In Ireland, many local authority Local Enterprise Offices facilitate Women in Business Networks (Murtagh et al. 2024d). Network organisations can be identified from civil society, hence policies that support civil society organisations appear important here also. For example, in the Czechia context the Czech Women’s Lobby has 41 sub-organisations (Vaishar, 2024). In Romania, empowering women economically, politically, and socially is supported by the Association for the Promotion of Women in Romania (Oprea and Incze, 2024).</p>
<p>Support is available for organisations that enable networks and networking in rural areas and/or farming that target women and/or specific needs relevant to women-led innovation</p>	<p>In relation to this action, examples can also be identified from civil society, hence policies that support organisations and their activities also appear important here. For example, in Italy it is noted that farming organisations can have female sub-organisations active in this area such as Confagricoltura Donna, Donne in Campo and Coldiretti Donne impresa (Sivini et al. 2024). Similarly in the Netherlands, farming organisations can have sub-organisations, such as the Dutch Farmers Association Woman and Enterprise (Vrouw en Bedrijf) division (Korthals Altes and Kang, 2024). In Slovenia, as part of the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men and the action ‘Strengthening the role of women in agriculture’ there is a focus on women’s rights and supporting organisations that assist with for example networking and knowledge transfer. Organisations that are supported include the Association of Farming Women of Slovenia (Lampič and Mikolič, 2024). In Ireland, under the agri-food sector policy Food Vision 2030 there is an action to promote and support women’s networks in the agri-food sector. The CERES women in agri-business leadership network is given as an example and was founded by women in the agri-business sector. As part of the Federal Programme for Rural Development and Regional Value Creation (BULEplus), in Germany the action ‘Digital.Networked – Strengthening Women in Volunteering’ aimed to strengthen the work of women’s associations and initiatives in the crisis situation caused by the pandemic with training and qualification measures in the field of digital association work (Meyer-Ohlendorf, L. 2024).</p>

Table A1. 3: Sub-Theme - 1.3 Access to Education and Up-Skilling Opportunities

Benchmarking principle: <i>Innovation can demand a range of skills and capacities, such as business skills and more specialist expertise. Innovators also need to stay aligned with new knowledge and changing enterprise needs. The enabling environment for women-led innovation includes appropriate supports to build skills and innovation capacities supporting participation and success in women-led innovation.</i>	
Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle	Illustrative examples
Women-led rural and/or farm entrepreneurship training programme exists	The EIT Food programme Empowering Women in Agrifood supports early-stage women-led business develop their entrepreneurial path. This is an EU co-funded program implemented in several Member States. It provides a six-month training, networking and mentoring programme. It is discussed in Ireland’s Policy Brief No. 2 (see Kang et al. eds. 2025). In Germany, as part of the programmes supporting women-led rural start-ups ‘Business Start-ups by Women in Rural Areas’ and ‘Innovative Measures for Women in Rural Areas’ they support further education and training (Meyer-Ohlendorf, 2024; also see German Policy Brief No. 2 in Kang et al. eds. 2025). Targeting training towards new entrepreneurs also emerges as important from the CoP workshop results (Annex 3).
Targeted upskilling programmes supporting women-led rural and/or farm innovation and entrepreneurship that take a peer-to-peer learning approach exist	In Ireland, ACORNS is peer-led support network for rural female entrepreneurs in Ireland. The focus is on helping nascent start-ups accelerate their establishment and development. It connects early-stage rural female entrepreneurs together and with 'lead entrepreneurs' to learn together and grow a business (Murtagh et al., 2024d; also see Ireland Policy Brief No. 2 in Kang et al. eds 2025). In Slovenia, the TERA Balancing Professional and Private Life in the Countryside project involved 20 mentoring pairs selected from the Association of Young Farmers and Association of Rural Women. They were trained then they offer workshops and individual mentoring to others through the programme (Lampič and Mikolič, 2024).
Measures are in place to assist improved gender balance in agricultural training programmes and education	A range of different types of measures would support this action. For example, the Netherlands Policy Brief No. 2 outlines some potential policy solutions, such as teacher training, national campaigns and to review/revise curricula (see Kang et al. eds 2025).

<p>Business and innovation training targets women in rural areas and/or farming and is designed with their specific needs in mind</p>	<p>Women leading innovations often need specialist skills as well as to gain new knowledge and adjust skills in line with changing enterprise needs. Digital and technological, as well as business and finance skills and capacities are two important wider areas of need. Italy's Policy Brief No. 1 proposes for example the establishment of Learning Centres for Rural and Farming Entrepreneurship that offer training tailored to women's needs (see Kang et al. eds. 2025). The EU funded Erasmus+ project Digital Entrepreneurship for Women (DEW) Programme (DEW) focused on developing training to support digital entrepreneurship skills for women entrepreneurs, particularly those from marginalised backgrounds (DEW, no date).</p>
<p>The wider knowledge and innovation system focuses on the needs of women involved in rural and/or farm innovation</p>	<p>A range of different types of measures would support this action. For example, the Netherlands CAP Strategic Plan CAP 2023-2027 states that within AKIS networks there should be a focus on networks aimed at (prospective) female farmers and issues specifically affecting this target group (Korthals Altes and Kang, 2024). Ireland's policy briefs No. 5 also highlights how specifically targeting women in AKIS spaces could happen, such as dedicated training for women on key issues. An example of a Teagasc QQI Level 5 Farm Safety and Assurance module run by Mountbellew Agricultural College is cited where the first round was targeted specifically to women working in farming (see Kang et al. eds. 2025).</p>

Table A1. 4: Sub-Theme - 1.4 Integrated and Wider Policies/Support Programmes

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>Programmes exist that support women's equal participation in rural and/or farm innovation that combine different aspects of the sub-themes 1.1 to 1.3.</i></p>	
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle</p>	<p>Illustrative examples</p>
<p>Targeted programmes exist to support women's increased participation in the rural and/or farm economy</p>	<p>Aligned with Spain's National Strategy for Gender Equality, and implemented through regional adaptations of the National Rural Development Program, various regions in Spain implement programs specifically aimed at empowering rural women, including support for entrepreneurship and innovation. The "Rural Women's Advancement Programs" can include training, mentorship, and financial assistance tailored to the needs of women in rural areas (Ricci and Martínez, 2024). In Germany, the long running programme in Baden-Württemberg 'Innovative Measure for Women in Rural Areas', encompasses funding, coaching and training measures.</p>

	Grants are available from €2,000 to €160,000 to facilitate enterprise start-up (Meyer-Ohlendorf, 2024; also see German Policy Brief No. 2 in Kang et al. eds. 2025).
There is a dedicated policy focus on rural and/or farm women's economic empowerment through women-led innovation and entrepreneurship	The FLIARA policy assessment found examples of policies and programmes that support women-led entrepreneurship. However, it also found that direct attention to the specific needs of rural and/or farm women-led innovation and entrepreneurship was often absent (Murtagh et al. 2024a). The need for dedicated attention emerged in our Italian CoP workshop discussions. One promising example identified through the FLIARA project is the Plan for the Promotion of Women in Rural Areas (2015-2018) in Spain developed within the Strategic Plan for Equal Opportunities 2014-2016. It aimed to promote the socio-economic inclusion, empowerment, and participation of women in rural Spain and provided for a series of support measures (Ministerio de Sanidad, Servicios Sociales e Igualdad y el Ministerio de Agricultura, Alimentación y Medio Ambiente, 2015).

Theme 2: Equal governance participation

Table A1. 5: Sub-Theme - 2.1 Politics

Benchmarking principle: <i>A range of measures exist to support gender balance in politics, tackling the issue directly (e.g. representation) and indirectly (stereotypes and norms).</i>	
Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle	Illustrative examples
Measures exist to support gender balance in elected representatives at different governance levels (e.g. local, regional, national)	In Romania, for national and European elections women must make up 20% of the electoral list (Oprea and Incze, 2024). In Slovenia a quota exists for electoral lists for parliamentary and local elections. There must be at least 40% candidates from the underrepresented gender (usually women) (Lampič and Mikolič, 2024). In Ireland, quotas exist for national politics where political parties must select at least 30% female candidates and the current programme for government commits to introduce measures for local government (Murtagh et al. 2024d). CoP workshop results point to the importance of quotas, as well as their presence at different governance levels (Annex 3).

Measures exist to support the increased visibility of women in politics and civil society	Visibility of women in politics is highlighted in Germany through prizes such as the Helene Weber Prize for recognition of outstanding achievements in local politics. Award winners are said to provide role models to other women. Another programme identified in the German context is the Landheldinnen program in Saxony that aims to promote the political participation of girls and young women in rural areas (Meyer-Ohlendorf, 2024). CoP workshop results point to the importance of a culture shift and changing mindsets to women's empowerment in decision-making spaces (Annex 3).
Measures exist to build women's skills and capacities to become involved in politics	The See Her Elected Programme in Ireland supports rural women engage in local democracy through the provision of training, mentoring and networking. The programme is funded through the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage (Murtagh et al. 2024d). More widely programmes can also emerge from civil society as highlighted by Romania through the example of the Women in Politics Program by National Democratic Institute (Oprea and Incze, 2024). This highlights how support for programmes to be delivered through civil society organisations is also important. CoP workshop results point to the importance of women's empowerment, such as through capacity building, so they can be better represented in decision-making spaces (Annex 3).

Table A1. 6: Sub-Theme - 2.2 Governance Spaces

Benchmarking principle: <i>Actions support women's representation in wider governance spaces that influence policy processes, such as policy design and implementation, as well as governance process in organisations relevant to women-led rural and farm innovation.</i>	
Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle	Illustrative examples
Dedicated mechanisms are in place to facilitate rural and/or farm women's issues are taken into account in policy.	In Slovenia, the Rural Women's Council is an advisory body within the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food and provides opinions and input on key decisions relating to women in rural areas (Lampič and Mikolič, 2024). The Irish government facilitated a National Dialogue on Women in Agriculture. The first National Dialogue in 2023 generated a 12-point Women in Agriculture Action Plan. The Women in Agriculture Working Group guides implementation of the action plan (Murtagh et al. 2024d)

Actions exist, such as quotas or targets, to increase gender balance in state governance spaces	The Irish government has a target to increase female participation in state boards to reach at least 40% (Murtagh et al. 2024d).
Actions exist, such as quotas or targets, to increase gender balance in other policy governance spaces	In Romania, the LAG partnership must have one organisation representing women's interests involved. In addition, at least 30% of representatives of the partnership must be young or female (Oprea and Incze, 2024). In Ireland a diversity of local actors and gender balanced representation is not mandatory, but must be aimed for in the LAG decision-making body (Murtagh et al. 2024d).
Measures exist to support gender balance in stakeholder organisations and private companies	In Italy there is a law on the representation of women on the board of directors and auditors of listed companies, as well as non-listed companies controlled by public companies. There is a quota in place and amendments have increased this from an initial 20% in 2011 to now 40%. (Sivini et al. 2024).

Theme 3: Gender related work-life conflicts, stereotypes and norms

Table A1. 7: Sub-Theme - 3.1 Work-Life Balance

Benchmarking principle: <i>A strong and stable support system is in place that supports work and family life balance. A strong and stable supports system is also in place that supports work and wider life balance, such as providing for leisure time.</i>	
Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle	Illustrative examples
Flexible and adequate parental leave exists that is paid, available to the self-employed and provides for sharing of leave among parents	Paid parental leave of 480 days is available to parents in Sweden. This is a universal, state administered scheme. Days can be transferred to people other than parents if one parent is absent, such as a grandparent. The scheme is also flexible. Days can be taken in blocks or over longer periods of time. The system is explored further in Sweden's Policy Brief No.1 (see Kang et al. eds. 2025; Roos and Ahl, 2024). CoP workshop results discussing the policy wish of 'work-family balance' emphasise that leave schemes should be designed with the needs of entrepreneurs and farmers in mind, with the Swedish approach discussed as a good model (Annex 3).

<p>Low cost and high-quality childcare places are guaranteed</p>	<p>In Sweden, municipalities must offer full-time pre-school care to all children over aged 1. Most municipalities also provide services for night or shift workers. After school activities must also be provided for children of school-going age. Schools and preschools serve a hot lunch and snacks. Preschool teachers must attend hold a specific 3.5-year education university level course. Fees are low. They are income tested and publicly subsidised (Roos and Ahl, 2024). The system is explored further in Sweden’s Policy Brief No.2 (see Kang et al. eds. 2025).</p>
<p>A publicly funded support system exists supporting farmers to take time off (e.g. sick leave, pregnancy leave, parental leave)</p>	<p>Finland’s farm relief system is publicly funded and supports farmers by providing substitute workers or self-arranged substitutes. It covers the costs of these workers. Circumstances covers are leave for holidays, illness, parental leave and pregnancy leave. The system is explored further in Sweden’s Policy Brief No.5 (see Kang et al. eds. 2025). More widely, CoP workshop results discussing the policy wish of ‘work-family balance’ point to the need for a culture shift around farming and entrepreneurial always-on work culture and the normalisation of taking time off (Annex 3).</p>

Table A1. 8: Sub-theme - 3.2 Stereotypes and Norms

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>Policies address increasing the visibility of women-led innovation and challenge gender stereotypes related to work-life and professions.</i></p>	
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle</p>	<p>Illustrative examples</p>
<p>Measures exist to support gender balance and address gender stereotypes and norms in rural economy sectors where women are under-represented</p>	<p>FLIARA identified policies in other sectors that could be assessed as models for development of similar measures relating to women-led rural innovation and farming. In Ireland’s policy assessment targeted support programmes to encourage careers for women in STEM sectors and engineering (e.g. THRIVE, Athena STEM and EXPLORE Engineering Alliance) were identified (Murtagh et al. 2024d). In Italy, the National Strategy for Gender Equality includes a range of supports for better women’s participation in STEM such as scholarships, strengthening education guidance services and reserving places in courses in STEM disciplines (Sivini et al. 2024).</p>
<p>Measures are in place to assist improving the</p>	<p>This action crosses over with wider goals of the FLIARA project. The FLIARA Visibility Campaign had this idea</p>

<p>visibility and recognition of existing women-led innovation in rural areas and farming</p>	<p>underpinning it, through a targeted communications campaign working to give increased visibility to women leading innovations (Martínez, 2025; Martínez and Perello, 2025).</p>
<p>Measures exist targeting emerging generations to impact a shift in traditional stereotypes and norms in relation to entrepreneurship, innovation and farming</p>	<p>The Netherlands Policy Brief No. 2 discusses the need for reforming educational curricula where these traditional stereotypes and norms are still seen, as well as promoting positive, diverse images of rural and farm women entrepreneurs. Promoting role models can be one action and way forward, such as highlighted by Czechia Policy Brief No.2 where the example of the Future is Female platform that is focused on various fields is highlighted (see Kang et al. eds. 2025). The FLIARA Ambassador model could provide a model for adaption to be supported in policy contexts. FLIARA Ambassadors (see European Policy Brief No. 1 in Kang et al. eds. 2025). More widely, CoP workshop results discussing education and skills suggested a need for supports targeting potential future entrepreneurs and budding entrepreneurs (Annex 3), also supporting the importance of targeting emerging generations.</p>

Theme 4: Gender related policy and legal frameworks

Table A1. 9: Sub-theme - 4.1 Gender Equality Laws, Policies and Tools

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>National laws, policies and governance systems provide a strong overarching framework from the top-down that ensures gender equality issues are taken account of in rural, farm and innovation policy.</i></p>	
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle</p>	<p>Illustrative examples</p>
<p>Gender mainstreaming is provided for in law and its practice is evident in rural, farm and innovation policy</p>	<p>In Germany, obligations to implement gender mainstreaming arise from international law and national constitutional law. Within the German CAP Strategic Plan there is strategic gender mainstreaming in the LEADER approach (Meyer-Ohlendorf, 2024). In Sweden, as part of achieving the goals of national gender equality policy, all policies at all stages are to be gender mainstreamed and this has been the case since 1994. The gender mainstreaming approach also means that specific targeted policies towards women in rural areas and farming are generally absent (Roos and Ahl, 2024).</p>

<p>Gender mainstreaming is supported by a strong institutional framework to ensure its implementation</p>	<p>Examples are not evident from FLIARA's assessment. In Sweden for example the national assessment reports gender mainstreaming guidance for government authorities has potential room for improvement (Roos and Ahl, 2024). A wider European report also echoes this observation. The European Court of Auditors (2021) outline the need for training and expertise building related to gender mainstreaming, implementation plans and clear objectives to meet.</p>
<p>Gender budgeting has a legal basis and is implemented following international good practice</p>	<p>FLIARA's policy assessment identified that in Romania gender budgeting is defined in the amended Gender Equality Law 2002, however the law does not contain an obligation to implement gender budgeting (Oprea, and Incze, 2024). Assessment of international good practice on gender budgeting's implementation has been carried out by the OECD. It publishes a Gender Budgeting Index comparing how countries implement gender budgeting across different dimensions as well as provides information on potential international good practices to learn from (OECD, 2023).</p>
<p>National gender equality policy devotes specific and adequate attention to the needs of rural and farm women</p>	<p>In Slovenia the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men includes an action on strengthening the role of women in agriculture. This helps to support organisations that assist with for example networking and knowledge provision such as the Association of Farming Women of Slovenia (Lampič and Mikolič, 2024; Murtagh et al. 2024a). In Spain, developed within the framework of the Strategic Plan for Equal Opportunities 2014-2016 was the Plan for the Promotion of Women in Rural Areas (2015-2018) in Spain (Ministerio de Sanidad, Servicios Sociales e Igualdad y el Ministerio de Agricultura, Alimentación y Medio Ambiente, 2015). CoP workshop results suggest an even stronger approach where a policy wish is suggested to create 'a national strategic plan' that addresses issues impacting rural and farm women, but with a bottom-up process and local governance guiding local implementation (Annex 3).</p>

Table A1. 10: Sub-theme - 4.2 Gender Equality in Rural, Farm and Innovation Policy

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>Strong and diverse policy actions support gender equality through policy implementation or specific policy design. Policy implementation is done in a gender-sensitive way and is designed in mind of current inequalities faced by women in rural areas and farming.</i></p>	
<p>Policy actions supporting the</p>	<p>Illustrative examples</p>

benchmarking principle	
<p>Selection criteria to qualify for support measures place priority on support for women</p>	<p>In Slovenia, in the CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027 intervention to support the establishment of young farmers' businesses women receive an additional 3 points in the selection criteria. In Slovenia supporting women is included within the selection criteria for assessing Local Development Strategies and awarded 2 out of 16 overall points. (Lampič and Mikolič, 2024). In Italy, in the CAP 2023-2027 intervention on investments in agricultural holdings for diversification into non-agricultural activities supporting women's enterprise is included as a priority (alongside young people) as part of the beneficiary selection criteria (Sivini et al. 2024). In Spain, in the CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027, while varying depending on the Managing Authority, it can still be observed that gender balance is strongly seen in a range of interventions, through applying specific selection criteria such as prioritising women-led projects (EU CAP Network, 2025). CoP workshop results discussing barriers in the existing policy support system suggest it is important to have a gender focus and awareness build into the support system, underlining the importance of this action, as well as this sub-theme overall (Annex 3).</p>
<p>A gender perspective is built into rural, farm and innovation policy monitoring and evaluation</p>	<p>Gender impact analysis of Rural Development Programmes would support this principle. For example, one can be identified from Catalonia (RegioPlus Consulting, 2022). Collecting strong if not all gender disaggregated data in policy performance and monitoring frameworks would also support this principle. However, for example, from looking at the European Commission's Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (PMEF) for CAP, in relation to SO8, there are no specific result indicators related to gender equality. There is one impact indicator that mentions gender (Murtagh et al. 2024a). The Netherlands Policy Brief No. 4 calls for gender policy key performance indicators in CAP, CAP Strategic Plan and LEADER (see Kang et al. eds. 2025).</p>
<p>Gender equality is an objective of rural, farm and innovation policies and includes mandatory minimum thresholds for implementation of this objective</p>	<p>Examples are not evident from FLIARA's assessment. However, there are examples of gender equality as part of objectives, without mandatory requirements. For example, CAP 2023-2027 SO8 objective is "to promote employment, growth, gender equality, including the participation of women in farming, social inclusion and local development in rural areas, including the circular bio-economy and sustainable forestry" (EU, 2021). In practice, the low level of commitment to addressing the issue of improving women's participation in farming and gender equality has been flagged as a concern in some policy assessments (e.g. EC, 2022).</p>

<p>Existence of policies promoting a gender balance in access to land, especially for new generations</p>	<p>Examples are not evident from FLIARA’s assessment, however the issue of access to land for women in farming was an issue identified by FLIARA. Korthals Altes (2020) finds access to land is a greater issue for women than men and in a European context where diverse inheritance laws exist still gender imbalanced inheritance outcomes are the common trend. This report also suggests that “if the outcomes are independent of specific regulations, a full solution will probably not be achieved by adapting new regulations; more may be needed” (Korthals Altes, 2020, p.60).</p>
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Theme 5: Rural sustainability

Table A1. 11: Sub-Theme - 5.1 Access to Resources

<p>Benchmarking principle: Policies support a strong enabling environment and access to resources to support improved rural and farm sustainability.</p>	
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle</p>	<p>Illustrative examples</p>
<p>Dedicated funding supports exist for innovation and entrepreneurship activities in areas where women-led innovation is more often found, such as agritourism, short food supply chains and the social economy</p>	<p>In Ireland a potential example could be the Rural Innovation and Development Fund that provides part-funding grants for projects in the Irish context and includes an agri-food tourism measure (Murtagh et al. 2024d). More widely laws that exist in the Italian context on social agriculture, agritourism and organic farming were identified as potential indirect supports for women-led innovation in farming, as well as a law regulating the establishment of farmers’ markets and the provision of spaces for them (Sivini et al. 2024). FLIARA policy briefs from the Netherlands also raise the issue of promoting more inclusive and sustainable agricultural practices (No.1) and better harnessing short supply chains (No.3) (see Kang et al. eds. 2025).</p>
<p>Dedicated funding supports exist for innovation and entrepreneurship activities in areas of future opportunity for women-led innovation such as digital and circular economies</p>	<p>Some potential examples can be pointed to from Ireland. The policy assessment for example pointed to the Enterprise Ireland Digital Transition Fund that focuses on SMEs as a potential support relevant to women-led innovation (Murtagh et al. 2024d). The Circular Economy Innovation Grant Scheme administered by the Department of Climate, Energy and the Environment (DCEE) aim to support growth of the circular economy and provides grants to support projects and enterprises (DCEE, 2025).</p>

Measures facilitate access to public land for sustainable farming and rural projects supporting sustainability	Public-private cooperations and partnerships can assist access to resources such as land. For example, as part of the Netherlands case study policy assessment the need for encouragement of partnerships between potential land users and local authorities to co-develop and manage community land is highlighted (Murtagh et al. 2024c). The issue is further raised in the Netherlands Policy Brief No. 1. Italy's Policy Brief No. 3 also raises similar issues, such as local authorities making public land available to women leading innovative projects and discusses examples of this from the Italian case studies (see Kang et al. eds. 2025).
Public policy support is facilitated by intermediaries supporting information provision and navigating application processes	As part of the Italy's case study policy assessment a new policy idea suggested is a 'hub' type facility that links women-leading innovators to information on supports, as well as assisting with applications. Ireland's case study policy assessment suggested an idea around intermediary support staff existing in-between funders and applicants to provide guidance and assistance (Murtagh et al. 2024c). CoP workshop results also underline the importance of this type of policy action with a number of the areas for policy improvement discussed identifying this type of policy action as important (Annex 3).

Table A1. 12: Sub-theme - 5.2 Co-creation and Cooperation

Benchmarking principle: <i>Policies support a strong enabling environment facilitating co-creation and cooperation to support improved rural and farm sustainability.</i>	
Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle	Illustrative examples
Dedicated supports exist to enable the formation of more collaborative organisational forms and membership based organisational models	A lack of cooperation was a gap FLIARA identified in the rural innovation ecosystem from the start of the project. The need for organisation of platforms for co-creation and cooperation emerged as a key measure needed to better promote women's contribution to sustainability innovations from the FLIARA futures research (Kuhmonen and Tembo, 2024b). One promising support example is pointed to in Policy Brief No. 8 from Sweden that identifies Coompanion, the

	<p>Swedish support function for cooperatives as an important support to advise and facilitate the establishment of cooperative business models. The potential wider value of more cooperative business models is also pointed to in the CoP workshop results. This is in the context of the policy wish of 'work-family life balance' where collaboration and shared ownership could reduce the burden on individuals from this respect (Annex 3).</p>
<p>A strong support framework is in place to support locally-led bottom-up development of the rural and/or farm economy</p>	<p>Our policy assessment identified how LEADER as a bottom-up locally-led approach to rural development has strong potential to support women-led innovation precisely because of the LEADER method. This can enable women-led innovation to respond to the challenges and opportunities of particular places (Murtagh et al. 2024a). However, the strength of the system is challenged by the fact highlighted in the EC Long Term Vision for Rural Areas taking stock of actions report where it is noted that LEADER must do more with less due to budget issues (EC, 2024). CoP workshop results also underline the importance of this type of policy action where one policy wish suggested was 'local co-created policy' that was discussed should include permanent discussion groups to allow for co-creation of policies with local communities, also with flagship projects supported by large funds (Annex 3).</p>
<p>A strong support framework is in place to support multi-actor cooperation projects</p>	<p>One example in this area is the EIP-AGRI programme. It provides funding for innovative, multi-actor, locally-led projects that address challenges and issues in the agri-food sector. Operational Groups provide a vehicle to bring together a range of people in farming and rural areas that hold diverse expertise and can then work together to collectively generate new knowledge and solutions. It is discussed in Ireland's Policy Brief No. 5 ((see Kang et al eds. 2025).</p>

Table A1. 13: Sub-theme - 5.3 Rural and Farm Regeneration

<p>Benchmarking principle: <i>Policies support a strong enabling environment to enhance the sustainable regeneration of the rural population and economy.</i></p>	
<p>Policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle</p>	<p>Illustrative examples</p>
<p>Strategies exist to support rural and/or farm development approaches</p>	<p>The National Strategy for Sustainable Regional Development in Sweden focuses on supporting innovation and takes a particular focus on</p>

<p>that embed a double or triple bottom line (social, environmental and economic) in their outcomes</p>	<p>microbusiness and social entrepreneurship (Roos and Ahl, 2024). In both Spain and Ireland national policies provide a framework for support of social enterprises, social innovation and entrepreneurship (Ricci and Martínez, 2024; Murtagh et al. 2024d). More widely a number of FLIARA policy briefs argue for a rethinking of the ethos supporting SMEs and the wider innovation support system, such as Sweden’s Policy Brief No. 6 and No. 8, as well as Finland’s Policy Brief No. 3 (see Kang et al eds. 2025). CoP workshop results also echo this idea where for example one policy wish was for an entrepreneurship system that includes and values alternative entrepreneur businesses. More broadly the idea of vision or value-based funding schemes was identified in the CoP workshop results (Annex 3) which could provide a specific policy measure to support the implementation of such strategies.</p>
<p>Strategies exist of relevance to rural areas and /or farming that focus on harnessing novel areas of under harnessed and future opportunity</p>	<p>In Spain, the National Plan for the Application of Agricultural Technologies focuses on the integration of advanced technologies in farming, such as precision agriculture, biotechnology, and digital solutions, to improve productivity, sustainability and resilience (Ricci and Martínez, 2024). More widely for example Ireland’s Policy Brief No. 4 discusses better leveraging digitalisation to support women-led rural and farm innovation.</p>
<p>Strategies exist to support rural and/or farm development approaches that support rural and farm generational renewal</p>	<p>In Italy, the National Strategy for Inner Areas is a place-based policy and multi-level (national, regional, local) governance. It aims to promote the local development, improved quality of life and economic well-being the population of "inner" areas and tackle the depopulation trend (Sivini et al. 2024).</p>
<p>Specific supports target rural return migration and entrepreneurship</p>	<p>The ‘Resto al Sud’ or ‘Remaining in the South’ programme operates in certain regions of Italy and supports the establishment and development of new entrepreneurial and freelance activities, excluding agricultural activities, providing maximum financing of €50,000 per applicant (Sivini et al. 2024). Romania’s Policy Brief No. 5 calls for support for women’s return to rural areas and promote female entrepreneurship (see Kang et al. eds. 2025).</p>

ANNEX 2: SAMPLE POLICY BENCHMARKING QUESTIONNAIRE

POLICY BENCHMARKING QUESTIONNAIRE

FLIARA Benchmarking Framework Theme 1

Equal Economic Participation

What: Targeted actions to support women's equal participation in farming, rural enterprise and innovation.

Rationale: Women-led rural and farm innovation needs to be supported to flourish through a diverse range of targeted supports that address women's needs such as improved access to finance, networks, knowledge and skills development opportunities. Within the support system, specific needs should also be addressed, such as targeted supports for particular groups of women (e.g. marginalised or young women), place-based opportunities (e.g. remote or mountain areas), specific innovation opportunities (ecological, digital, social enterprise) or specific business-stage (set-up, expansion).

PART 1: BENCHMARKING ASSESSMENT

Sub-theme: 1.1 Access to finance

Benchmarking principle: A diverse targeted support system is in place to facilitate access to finance for women-led rural and/or farm enterprise and innovation. It is appropriate and designed in light of the distinct needs, challenges and characteristics of women-led rural and farm innovation. This support framework acts both as an incentive and support.

Assessment of policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:

1.1a: Existence of state-supported micro credit scheme that targets women or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation.

Please provide an assessment of the 1.1a policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

1.1b: Existence of targeted grants exist that support the development of women-led innovation development or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation.

Please provide an assessment of the 1.1b policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

1.1c Existence of interest free or low-cost finance that targets women or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation.

Please provide an assessment of the 1.1c policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

1.1d: Finance support programmes target specific stages of women-led innovation development or more specifically women-led rural and/or farm innovation.

Please provide an assessment of the 1.1d policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

Sub-theme: 1.2 Access to networks

Benchmarking principle: Networks are a central part of the enabling environment for women-led innovation. Policy actions directly support networking as well as indirectly support activities (e.g. organisations, projects) that provide spaces to network for women in rural and farm innovation.

Assessment of policy actions supporting the benchmarking principle:

1.2a: Women-led rural and/or farm enterprise networking supports exist

Please provide an assessment of the 1.2a policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

1.2b: Support is available for networks and networking for women involved in innovation and entrepreneurship

Please provide an assessment of the 1.2b policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

1.2c: Support is available for organisations that enable networks and networking in rural areas and/or farming that target women and/or specific needs relevant to women-led innovation

Please provide an assessment of the 1.2c policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

Sub-theme: 1.3 Access to education and up-skilling opportunities

Benchmarking principle: *Innovation can demand a range of skills and capacities, such as business skills and more specialist expertise. Innovators also need to stay aligned with new knowledge and changing enterprise needs. The enabling environment for women-led innovation includes appropriate supports to build skills and innovation capacities supporting participation and success in women-led innovation.*

1.3a: Women-led rural and/or farm entrepreneurship training programme exists

Please provide an assessment of the 1.3a policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

1.3b: Targeted upskilling programmes supporting women-led rural and/or farm innovation and entrepreneurship that take a peer-to-peer learning approach exist

Please provide an assessment of the 1.3b policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

1.3c: Measures are in place to assist improved gender balance in agricultural training programmes and education

Please provide an assessment of the 1.3c policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

1.3d: Business and innovation training targets women in rural areas and/or farming and is designed with their specific needs in mind

Please provide an assessment of the 1.3d policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

1.3e: The wider knowledge and innovation system focuses on the needs of women involved in rural and/or farm innovation

Please provide an assessment of the 1.3e policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

Sub-theme: 1.4: Integrated and wider policies/support programmes

Benchmarking principle: *Programmes exist that support women's equal participation in rural and/or farm innovation that combine different aspects of the sub-themes 1.1 to 1.3.*

1.4a: Targeted programmes exist to support women's increased participation in the rural and/or farm economy

Please provide an assessment of the 1.4a policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

1.4b: There is a dedicated policy focus on rural and/or farm women's economic empowerment through women-led innovation and entrepreneurship

Please provide an assessment of the 1.4b policy action in relation to the questions below:

Do these types of measure(s) exist? Please provide short description

If measure(s) do exist, are they considered to work well and why?

If measures do exist, are they considered to have disadvantages or room for improvement in their design or implementation?

If measure(s) do not exist, are they considered needed or appropriate in your context?

ANNEX 3: COP WORKSHOP FINDINGS

A3.1 WORKSHOP METHODOLOGY

The FLIARA CoP Network WP4 Task ‘T4.3 Benchmarking and Policy Design’ involved workshops held alongside the four FLIARA CoP Network events. The workshops had two phases.

Phase 1 involved a workshop held at the CoP Galway, Ireland and CoP Ljubljana, Slovenia. The data collected from these first two workshops was analysed for the deliverable D4.3: Initial Benchmarking Report (Murtagh et al. 2024c). This brought the CoP workshop data together with insights from the WP1 policy assessment and identification of policy needs emerging from WP3 case studies. The analysis of this data allowed the identification of key areas of policy improvement which were brought forward to phase 2.

Phase 2 involved a second set of two workshops held at CoP Calabria, Italy and CoP Växjö, Sweden. The workshop approach was built around 13 areas for policy improvement (Figure A3. 1) and two tasks. To set the scene, an introductory presentation provided a brief explanation of each topic before moving into the two tasks at the core of the workshops.

Areas of future policy improvement to better support women-led innovation?
Specific enabling conditions for women-led farm and rural innovation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Improve access to finance</i> • More tailored supports to different phases and patterns of enterprise development • Better access to networks and peer support • <i>Advance education and skills training for women innovators</i> • <i>Address barriers specific to particular groups of women</i> • Address more specific barriers to women-led farm innovation
The policy support system
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>More innovative policy design</i> • <i>Address barriers in the existing policy support system</i> • <i>Greater policy focus on women-led innovation as a lever for improving rural sustainability</i>
Rural resources, social and cultural conditions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address wider rural development issues • <i>Address domestic work distribution and work equity</i> • Address traditional gender norms and stereotypes • <i>Better representation of women in decision making</i>
<i>italics = discussed in workshops</i>

Figure A3. 1: Areas for Policy Improvement

Task 1 focused on gaining insight on the priorities for policy from the areas for policy improvement identified from deliverable D4.3: Initial Benchmarking Report (Murtagh et al. 2024c). Each participant was asked to rate the areas for policy improvement using

the rating questionnaire (see **Figure A3. 2** and Figure A3. 3). This was an exploratory approach intended only to gain broad insights into the areas of higher or lower priority. The results are reported for each CoP below.

Country of residence: _____

Type of organisation (e.g. enterprise, university): _____

Role (e.g. researcher, entrepreneur): _____

Policy Improvement Areas		Comments - optional
Please circle a rating between 1 and 5 to indicate how important you feel it is to address this issue to better support women-led rural and farm innovation 1: Very important 2: Important 3: Moderately important 4: Slightly important 5: Not important		
Improve access to finance e.g. more diverse types of finance are available such as grants, low-cost loans, micro-finance, tax credits	1 2 3 4 5	
More tailored supports to different phases and patterns of enterprise development e.g. supports tailored to for example start-up, scale-up or slow growing businesses	1 2 3 4 5	
Better access to networks and peer support e.g. mentoring, access to more diverse networks at different scales (local to international), specialist peer-to-peer learning spaces (e.g. organic farming, social enterprise)	1 2 3 4 5	
Advance education and skills training for women innovators e.g. digital and technological or business and finance skills	1 2 3 4 5	
Address barriers specific to particular groups of women e.g. targeted supports for young women, older women, marginalised women	1 2 3 4 5	
Address more specific barriers specific to women-led farm innovation e.g. barriers related to access to land, machinery and technology design	1 2 3 4 5	
More innovative policy design e.g. enhancement of integrated, place-based, locally-led supports or targeted supports for women-led innovation	1 2 3 4 5	

Figure A3. 2: Rating Questionnaire Page 1

Policy Improvement Areas		Comments - optional
Please circle a rating between 1 and 5 to indicate how important you feel it is to address this issue to better support women-led rural and farm innovation 1: Very important 2: Important 3: Moderately important 4: Slightly important 5: Not important		
Address barriers in the existing policy support system: e.g. bureaucracy, complex application processes, funding timescales, improve information availability	1 2 3 4 5	
Greater policy focus on women-led innovation as a lever for improving rural sustainability e.g. diversification of the rural and farm economy, harness opportunities for innovation in novel sectors such as digital, circular and bioeconomy	1 2 3 4 5	
Address wider rural development issues: e.g. improve access to infrastructure (digital, communications) and services (childcare, public transport)	1 2 3 4 5	
Address domestic work distribution and work equity: e.g. Policies supporting work-life balance (parental leave) or time-off (farm relief schemes)	1 2 3 4 5	
Address traditional gender norms and stereotypes e.g. patriarchal attitudes, gender norms related to career choices	1 2 3 4 5	
Better representation of women in decision making e.g. in areas such as politics, representative organisations, government boards	1 2 3 4 5	
Anything missing? add your 'wildcard here...	1 2 3 4 5	

Figure A3. 3: Rating Questionnaire Page 2

Task 2 focused on specific areas of future policy improvement allowing for more in depth exploration of future policy options and needs in these areas. From the 13 areas, a set was allocated to each table. Participants first discussed the topics allocated to their table to choose one to focus on for deeper discussion. Once chosen, participants reflected for a few moments and wrote their policy wishes on sticky notes. The idea of 'policy wish' was intended to gain insight into the key, most essential and urgent changes to future policy they would like to see. The group then discussed these policy wishes and chose

one to explore in greater detail, focusing on how it could be achieved through specific actions. The format that guided the structure of these discussions is seen in Figure A3.4.

<i>Topic:</i>			
	<i>More Innovative Policy Design</i>		
Policy Wish	How? Specific Policy Measures/Approaches?	Who?	Timeframe
Local co-created policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement representation of rural and local women in decision making • Tailored farm territory policy. • Needs bigger funds, lots of little projects have less impact, need bigger longer term funds/projects. • Funds dedicated to women and addressing local needs • Find ways to address the challenge to design policy and listen to all target groups. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many Cross-cutting Domains • Government; Municipalities • EU Level organisations and National Administrations funding projects 	ASAP

Figure A3.4: Format for Policy Design Discussions and Sample Topic

In practice, the policy wish discussed in depth was most often a synthesis of different policy wishes emerging from the first reflections of participants. They mostly discussed one wish in depth. Sometimes a second was also discussed if time permitted. The main results of these discussions are outlined for the two CoPs in the sections below. All areas for future policy improvement were not discussed in detail and those in italics in Figure A3.1 above were the topics chosen by participants for in depth discussion. Overall, eight of the 13 topics were discussed in detail in the workshops, as chosen by participants.

Each workshop had four groups to allow for small group discussions. Participants were pre-allocated to groups with the aim to ensure a mix of participants from different backgrounds (women leading innovations, consortium, wider stakeholders) and cross-national perspectives. This aimed to allow for idea exchange, cross-fertilization of ideas and co-creation of results. An overview of participants at each CoP is provided in Table A3.1 below.

Table A3. 1: Overview of CoP Workshop Participants

CoP country	host	Total number of workshop participants (including notetakers and facilitators)	Countries represented (number of participants)
CoP Calabria, Italy		26	Finland (1), Germany (1), Ireland (2), Italy (13), Slovenia (5), Spain (2), Sweden (2)
CoP Växjö, Sweden		23	Czechia (1), Finland (4), Germany (2), Greece (1), Ireland (5), Italy (2), Netherlands (1), Sweden (7),

A3.2 ITALY COP WORKSHOP RESULTS

A3.2.1: Rating questionnaire

The results indicate a strong consensus that policy action is needed across several areas to better support women-led innovation in rural and farming contexts, with all items rated as at least ‘Important.’ This approach was used to gain broad insights into the areas of higher or lower priority and overall underlined the importance of a diverse range of policy areas to women-led rural and farm innovation. This also further reinforces the importance of comprehensive benchmarking frameworks. More specifically the results show highest priorities centre on improving the policy support ecosystem itself, particularly by tailoring supports to different stages of enterprise development (start-up, scale-up, and slower growth pathways) and reducing existing barriers such as bureaucracy, complex application processes, unclear information, and restrictive funding timescales. Participants also highlighted the importance of strengthening networks and peer learning opportunities, alongside addressing social barriers including traditional gender norms and underrepresentation of women in decision-making. Access to finance, infrastructure, and services such as childcare and transport were also viewed as important structural enablers. While areas such as education and skills, targeted supports for specific groups of women, work–life balance policies, innovative policy design, and farm-specific barriers were rated slightly lower, they nonetheless remain ‘Moderately important,’ suggesting that respondents see value in a comprehensive, multi-dimensional policy approach rather than isolated interventions. Overall, the findings point to a need for both universal reform and targeted measures that collectively enhance capacity, visibility, resources, and cultural change for women innovators in rural areas.

Table A3. 2: Italy CoP Rating Questionnaire Results

Area for policy improvement	Average rating By category*	Average rating
More tailored supports to different phases and patterns of enterprise development e.g. supports tailored to for example start-up, scale-up or slow growing business	Important	1.92
Address barriers in the existing policy support system: e.g. bureaucracy, complex application processes, funding timescales, improve information availability	Important	2.04
Better access to networks and peer support e.g. mentoring, access to more diverse networks at different scales (local to international), specialist peer-to-peer learning spaces (e.g. organic farming, social enterprise)	Important	2.23
Address traditional gender norms and stereotypes e.g. patriarchal attitudes, gender norms related to career choices	Important	2.27
Better representation of women in decision making e.g. in areas such as politics, representative organisations, government boards	Important	2.30
Improve access to finance e.g. more diverse types of finance are available such as grants, low-cost loans, micro-finance, tax credits	Important	2.31
Address wider rural development issues: e.g. improve access to infrastructure (digital, communications) and services (childcare, public transport)	Important	2.35
Advance education and skills training for women innovators e.g. digital and technological or business and finance skills	Important	2.46
Address barriers specific to particular groups of women e.g. targeted supports for young women, older women, marginalised women	Moderately important	2.52
Address domestic work distribution and work equity: e.g. Policies supporting work-life balance (parental leave) or time-off (farm relief schemes)	Moderately important	2.52
More innovative policy design e.g. enhancement of integrated, place-based, locally-led supports or targeted supports for women-led innovation	Moderately important	2.56
Address more specific barriers specific to women-led farm innovation e.g. barriers related to access to land, machinery and technology design	Moderately important	2.68
Greater policy focus on women-led innovation as a lever for improving rural sustainability e.g. diversification of the rural and farm economy, harness opportunities for innovation in novel sectors such as digital, circular and bioeconomy	Moderately important	2.69
<p><i>Notes:</i> *Scale used in questionnaire: 1: Very important; 2: Important; 3: Moderately important; 4: Slightly important; 5: Not important. Ratings included above reflect rounded averages. Number of respondents = 27 (Finland (1), Germany (1), Ireland (2), Italy (15), Romania (1), Slovenia (4), Spain (1), Sweden (2))</p>		

A3.2.2: Areas for policy improvement and policy wishes

In Italy, the four groups were allocated a mix of topics of future policy improvement to choose from. All 13 areas for future policy improvement were included. For the four chosen areas, the main discussions and policy wishes are outlined below.

More innovative policy design

Participants discussed how innovative policy design that is place-based and locally-led can be a powerful approach. This means a range of interlinked local issues can be targeted with one policy. However, it was also discussed how the policy design process is also critical where this, in addition, needs innovation to ensure the issues identified and actions to address them are appropriately tailored. This led participants to develop and agree on discussing **the policy wish ‘local co-created policy’** in more depth. Key points emerging were:

- *Mechanism to allow for co-creation of policies with local communities:* The challenge of designing policy of this nature and listening to all target groups was evident. The idea of creating permanent discussion groups to develop local policies was put forward. The need for gender balanced representation and women’s involvement in the decision-making mechanisms of such groups was also raised as part of this. Women’s empowerment was also pointed to as an important part of this type of local policy process.
- *Actions to build interest and capacity in participation in local development:* The need for activation measures to generate enthusiasm and motivation among the local community towards shaping local development emerged as important to realising this policy wish. One example discussed was the asset of strong local heritage, history and culture in rural areas, however also sometimes a lack of interest and understanding of its value among the young population. One potential policy action to help address this discussed was some form of youth mentoring programme focused on building capacity to harness local assets and address local needs. More broadly another action discussed was a dedicated support office that assists local people, and specifically targeting women, to develop innovative projects that serve local needs and opportunities.
- *Flagship projects and large funds:* Participants discussed how there is potentially a strong role as part of this policy approach for bigger funds that allow for longer term development. More short-term, small-scale funds and projects were thought to not serve communities and innovators well in this type of local development approach.

Greater policy focus on women-led innovation as a lever for improving rural sustainability

The need for a new value system underpinning the entrepreneurial support framework was an issue underpinning this discussion. Central to this new value system is the need to better value and support alternative or non-profit driven businesses and sustainability goals. The need for support for different business stages (e.g. start-up, post-start-up) was also a broad emerging theme. The participants developed and agreed on discussing **two policy wishes ‘start-up and growth financial support for women entrepreneurs’** and **‘entrepreneurship system that includes and values alternative entrepreneur businesses’** in more depth. Key points emerging were:

Start-up and growth financial support for women entrepreneurs

- *Ring-fence budgets for women-led innovation with a focus on specific phases of development:* The need for an increase in the availability of grants for women-led business in farming and rural areas was identified. It was also argued that a specific budget should be allocated for start-up and early growth phases. The importance of easy access to funds, that the process is not highly cumbersome with long timeframes, was also highlighted. Focusing on early growth phases and after initial start-up was also pointed to. This could be where for example funds for women entrepreneurs being in business 3+ years are available to help sustain the business and ensure survival. Support for bilateral entrance (i.e. for people without background in farming) was also highlighted as important.
- *Locally driven and knowledge-based funds:* The idea was also discussed that this type of funding system, and the outcomes it aims to work towards, can also be driven by a strong wider local knowledge base. This could be supported by market research by education/research institutions and/or cross-sectoral local interest groups (e.g. Handicraft organisations, Chamber of Commerce).

Entrepreneurship system that includes and values alternative entrepreneur businesses

- *Culture shift in the entrepreneurship support system:* The need for a change of ethos underpinning the entrepreneurship support system was pointed to. It was argued there is room for expanding the focus beyond STEM and placing greater emphasis on more 'alternative' forms of entrepreneurship, such as social enterprise. This would then also drive a different focus on assessment criteria for funding. Sustainability goals should filter through this system at all levels from local to global. It would also call for social benefits to be valued in the same way as economic benefits. For example, it is pointed to that regenerative projects should always be granted funding, because even if they fail, they still generate some positive impacts. More research showcasing the value of alternative, value-based, socially-driven projects is also pointed to as important to assist this shift.
- *Ring-fence budgets for sustainability innovation:* A marker of how the entrepreneurship support system values alternative businesses should be that there is dedicated budget for sustainability innovations. For example, the discussions included suggesting that half of state support should go to alternative businesses.

Address barriers in the existing policy support system

Participants discussed the importance of changes to the support system to ensure it functions better to support those it intends to benefit. This led participants to develop and agree on discussing **two interlinked policy wishes 'reducing bureaucracy - coherence, simplification, greater unity'** and **'gender focus in the support system'** in more depth. Key points emerging were:

Reducing bureaucracy - coherence, simplification, greater unity

- *Large and strong degree of simplification:* The discussion emerging from this group called for strong changes to the policy support system based around the

ethos of simplification. This would impact on a range of areas including calls for proposals, application processes and eligibility criteria. It was also pointed out that the level of funding should match the complexity of the requirements to apply for it. For example, funding for small projects should have a short and quick application process. Greater local control was also discussed as important in this new system where funding at local level is also monitored at local level.

- *Support to assist beneficiaries:* Those who need policy support do not always have specific skills or experience in navigating the system. It was argued that the policy support system needs to operate with an awareness of this issue. This calls for a centralised information system with for example good quality, clear information and documentation in an accessible language. When it comes to applications for funding, it is important that processes are simplified and only necessary information is collected.

Gender focus in the support system

- *A gender aware support system:* It was argued the policy support system should also include specific targeted supports for women. In addition, there should be efforts to improve how the system functions from within to improve gender awareness. This could include measures such as gender training for policy makers, as well as women as key stakeholders involved in the policy design process.

Address barriers specific to particular groups of women

Participants started by discussing a range of issues impacting rural and farm women, such as access to land, childcare, finance, accessing training, specific issues that face more isolated women and improving eco-feminist perspectives in policy frameworks. This led to the question of what policies can address this diverse range of demands. It was felt that these issues can get lost in wider policies such as rural development policy or different sector-focused or social policies. A national plan for rural women emerged as an approach that would see a range of rural women's needs on the national agenda. This led to the **policy wish 'A national strategic plan to address the issues raised collectively'** in more depth. Key points emerging were:

- *Overarching national plan, however with a bottom-up approach:* Participants outlined how an umbrella national plan should be in place that addresses key issues and actions. Central government should lead the development of the national plan. However, importantly, it should be developed in consultation with key actors at different governance levels, such as LAGs, mayors, bodies with responsibility for equal opportunities, women's professional associations, as well as wider relevant local and regional stakeholders. Paired with this umbrella national plan, a bottom-up process should guide local implementation so that actions are aligned to women's current needs and local territorial differences.
- *Local planning groups support the bottom-up approach:* Participants discussed how the bottom-up process should be underpinned by a local project team. This process should ensure that actions are aligned to the national plan, while also tailored to local needs. A local action plan should be developed to guide this

process. This would form an important vehicle for policy implementation. The actors that are involved in developing this plan should be those with direct, close and continuous relationships with their territories and localities. Governance of this local action plan's implementation should involve women in the decision-making processes.

- *Placement outreach offices*: Participants discussed how an outreach aspect should also be a key part of local implementation. This would work to ensure women are aware of the policy supports available to assist them. It was discussed how women's daily life commitments and/or their isolation can be a barrier to seeking out relevant information and opportunities. As part of this system, a local figure and/or mobile laboratory could play a role in providing information and connecting women to supports. Potentially this is where groups such as women's professional associations and LAGs could play a strategic role.

A3.3 SWEDEN COP WORKSHOP RESULTS

A3.3.1: Rating questionnaire

The rating questionnaire approach was again used in Sweden to gain broad insights into the policy improvement areas of higher or lower priority. The results again overall underlined the importance of a diverse range of policy areas to women-led rural and farm innovation, also underlining the importance of comprehensive benchmarking frameworks. More specifically, these results show a prioritisation of financial and policy innovation measures to support women-led innovation in rural and farming contexts. Improving access to diverse forms of finance received the highest importance rating, closely followed by a strong call for more innovative, integrated, and locally responsive policy design. Respondents also emphasised the importance of strengthening networks, peer support, and addressing bureaucratic and structural barriers within existing policy systems, alongside providing more tailored supports for different stages of enterprise development. Broader issues such as infrastructure, representation in decision-making, and sector-specific challenges in farming were also rated as important, while actions targeting particular sub-groups of women were seen as moderately important. Overall, the findings suggest that respondents favour an integrated policy approach combining improved financial access, smarter policy mechanisms, and stronger ecosystems of support.

Table A3. 3: Sweden CoP Rating Questionnaire Results

Area for policy improvement	Average rating By category*	Average rating
Improve access to finance e.g. more diverse types of finance are available such as grants, low-cost loans, micro-finance, tax credits	Very important	1.35
More innovative policy design e.g. enhancement of integrated, place-based, locally-led supports or targeted supports for women-led innovation	Very important	1.40
Better access to networks and peer support e.g. mentoring, access to more diverse networks at different scales (local to international), specialist peer-to-peer learning spaces (e.g. organic farming, social enterprise)	Important	1.55
Address barriers in the existing policy support system: e.g. bureaucracy, complex application processes, funding timescales, improve information availability	Important	1.55
More tailored supports to different phases and patterns of enterprise development e.g. supports tailored to for example start-up, scale-up or slow growing business	Important	1.65
Greater policy focus on women-led innovation as a lever for improving rural sustainability e.g. diversification of the rural and farm economy, harness opportunities for innovation in novel sectors such as digital, circular and bioeconomy	Important	1.70
Address wider rural development issues: e.g. improve access to infrastructure (digital, communications) and services (childcare, public transport)	Important	1.75
Better representation of women in decision making e.g. in areas such as politics, representative organisations, government boards	Important	1.75
Address more specific barriers specific to women-led farm innovation e.g. barriers related to access to land, machinery and technology design	Important	1.85
Advance education and skills training for women innovators e.g. digital and technological or business and finance skills	Important	1.95
Address domestic work distribution and work equity: e.g. Policies supporting work-life balance (parental leave) or time-off (farm relief schemes)	Important	1.95
Address traditional gender norms and stereotypes e.g. patriarchal attitudes, gender norms related to career choices	Important	2.10
Address barriers specific to particular groups of women e.g. targeted supports for young women, older women, marginalised women	Moderately important	2.50
<p><i>Notes:</i> *Scale used in questionnaire: 1: Very important; 2: Important; 3: Moderately important; 4: Slightly important; 5: Not important. Ratings included above reflect rounded averages. Number of respondents = 20 (Czechia (1), Finland (4) Germany (1), Greece (1), Ireland (3), Italy (2), Netherlands (1), Sweden (7))</p>		

A3.3.2: Areas for policy improvement and policy wishes

In Sweden, any topics already discussed in Italy were omitted from the choices participants selected from for in depth discussion. This resulted in the four groups having a smaller number of topics to choose from. Omitting the topics already discussed in Italy also ensured that data was gathered on a greater range of topics. This decision was also informed by the results of the rating questionnaire from Italy and how it broadly showed

the importance of all the areas for policy improvement. For the four chosen areas, the main discussions and policy wishes are outlined below.

Advance education and skills training for women innovators

The participants developed and agreed on discussing **the policy wish ‘innovative thinking support (in terms of education and training courses)’** in more depth. The core idea embedded in this wish was better utilisation of novel approaches to education as well as tailoring of education to specific needs of entrepreneurs and women leading innovations in rural and farming contexts. The discussion yielded practical and specific actions in terms of teaching pedagogy and wider approaches to course design. Key points emerging were:

- *Skills and knowledge building support for new entrepreneurs:* In the early stages of entrepreneurship and innovation, finding the right support, information and skills can be an important enabler. Actions aligned to this suggested were that an information package is provided to all newly registered entrepreneurs on key issues such as requirements when taking on employees, available support and networks. It was also suggested that a free business course for all new entrepreneurs should be available, covering for example rights, responsibilities and support available to entrepreneurs. It was also discussed that this type of course could also be tailored to the needs of women leading innovations in rural and farming contexts. More widely, the skills and learning environment for entrepreneurs were also discussed, with the need for approaches such as life-long and practice-based learning being important.
- *Skills and knowledge building support for budding entrepreneurs:* Targeting education so that those with aspirations for entrepreneurship can be supported to develop also emerge as important. This could include paid internships to provide practice-based learning. The idea of exchange programmes within university courses where students have options to explore subjects across facilities rather than only in their core field of study was suggested. This was with the idea to allow for cross fertilisation of knowledge and how this can generate ideas for innovations. Another action discussed was direct connections between innovators and schools/universities where there is a space for idea exchange and potential collaborations. More widely also creating innovation incubation spaces was discussed as important, such through events where women can share their innovation ideas with different actors, receive feedback and potentially establish collaborations.
- *Skills and knowledge building support to inspire future entrepreneurs:* Actions to spotlight and give visibility to women innovators in rural areas, to inspire women and the young generation to engage in innovation, were also an important part of this policy wish. Actions could take different forms, such as: harnessing the media to renew the rural image; having role models visit schools and speak to students providing real world inspiration; and increasing the business and innovation focus in school education, such as through offering specific courses.

Better representation of women in decision making

Initial discussions on this topic centred around debating the best policy approach to address the issue. Debate occurred around whether hard measures such as quotas or softer measures such as capacity building to enable women to engage in decision-making were the best way forward. Emerging from the concluding discussions was the need for both soft and hard measures. The participants developed and agreed on discussing **two policy wishes** ‘**mandatory gender balance**’ and ‘**female empowerment**’ in more depth. Key points emerging were:

Mandatory gender balance

- *Quotas and the scope of action:* The need for a quota system where there is 50:50 representation was a clearly emerging policy need from the discussions. The scope was viewed as not just that of politics, but also a wider governance issue where a mandatory quota system should also be in place on the boards of organisations and companies. Context was also discussed to impact the feasibility of quotas being introduced. Political will for such a policy was felt to exist to a different extent depending on the context. The potential role of a gender proofing mechanism to make issues clear and be a trigger for action was also discussed as a potential way to overcome this.
- *Scale of action:* In relation to politics and representation, a national framework of law was discussed as important to underpin action. In terms of bringing in this policy change, it was discussed how it could first be made law at local levels and then initiated at national levels. However, this pathway was also debated where the discussion also suggested the effect would be more immediate if implemented at both levels concurrently.

Female empowerment

- *Capacity building for women:* The need for measures to support building women’s confidence, capacity and skills to become more active in decision-making and governance spaces was identified. Measures discussed were mentorship programs, leadership training, network building and role models to increase visibility of successful examples of women leaders as inspiration and to change attitudes. More specifically, engaging with young people through these measures was also noted as important.
- *Culture shift and changing mindsets:* The wider need for a gender dimension to become part of what representation and governance means in practice was also a key point. It was discussed how it is not just women that can represent women’s needs in decision-making. Men can also represent women’s perspectives too. The need for actions to challenge traditional gender norms, such as providing training, as well as addressing issues through the school curriculum, were discussed.

Improve access to finance

The discussion around access to finance and the existing finance support system emphasised the need for adjustments as part of the existing system. This included the

need for more tailored finance support measures, simplified and efficient processes of application and funding receipt, as well as more flexible rules being applied to support measures so they can respond better to the individual needs of rural and farm entrepreneurs, as well as specific rural places. Financial pressures on entrepreneurs from the wider economic environment they do business in were also discussed, such as the extent of tax liabilities. The impact of the financial state of the enterprise on generational renewal was also discussed and the need to pay back loans over shorter periods to avoid debt transfer on generational renewal. Discussion also covered issues related to both public grants and finance mechanisms such as loans. The participants developed and agreed on the **policy wish of 'a more diversified funding system'** to discuss in more depth. An important part of this more diversified funding system was also adding elements that enabled the existing system to work better. Key points emerging were:

- *Support system for enabling uptake of funding:* Participants discussed how there can be a negative feeling about finance supports such as the feeling of 'going begging' and loss of motivation due to, for example, bureaucracy and complex criteria. It was also noted that the funding application process is more difficult for first-time applicants and those newer to business. This calls for support in the system to facilitate the funding application process, such as a dedicated advisor to support navigating funding processes. Networking events locally to connect potential funders and investors with innovators were also discussed, and not just as sporadic events, but that happen on a regular schedule and are well promoted helping to support an innovative culture. This system would also support greater consistency in how rules are applied by different regional agencies (such as LEADER LAGs) administering funds and sharing of knowledge among them, as well as better data and monitoring of who benefits from schemes, particularly relating to gender balance.
- *Local decision making:* Participants discussed the need for greater power and decision-making at local levels and a greater role for multi-level governance. Local holders of power, such as mayors, can have vision but also can lack capacity to initiate changes based on this. It was felt that funding decision makers need to understand issues and needs from the local business perspective. Local decision making should also be allowed to have some flexibility around how decisions are made. For example, in relation to place based funds, if valid applicants are just outside the eligible area, there should be a process that enables them to still be considered for funding. Part of this type of governance should also work towards longer term goals and targets that are not impacted by political power changes, but link to wider issues and grand challenges such as sustainability.
- *Innovative, novel finance mechanisms:* A key part of this more diversified funding system that was discussed was the place of more innovative, novel finance support mechanisms. Better funding tied to specific business phases was discussed. Wider ideas discussed were public-private partnerships for finance such as legacy inheritance foundations and local benefactor trust funds. Angel investors for women and raising finance for local economic development by taxing those with wealth was also discussed. The idea of vision-based or value-

based funding that sees funds linked to a bigger picture, such as sustainability goals or social benefits, and sees value-based objectives filter into funding schemes was also discussed. The point was also made that the funding system needs to better assess risk and have room to fund novel ideas that can seem like risky investments. This calls for more novel assessment indicators for funding eligibility.

Address domestic work distribution and work equity

The importance of policies that support women farmers and rural entrepreneurs to balance family and professional responsibilities, as well as more broadly achieve work-life balance through policy that supports wider time off, was made clear in this group's discussions. The participants developed and agreed on the **policy wish 'work-family balance'** to discuss in more depth. Key points emerging were:

- *The importance of leave schemes that are designed with the needs of entrepreneurs and farmers in mind:* The Swedish model of parental leave emerged in the discussion as embedding many of these needs – that it provides for paid, shared and flexible parental leave. The need for flexibility, in particular around stopping work completely, was also clear in the specific case of farmers and entrepreneurs when compared to the needs of employees. The need for income support, that leave is paid, also emerged as very important. For example, in the face of volatile farm incomes and supports, a paid leave scheme appears even more critical in the case of farming.
- *Incentives for generational renewal:* The need to think cross-generationally in farming in relation to work-family life balance was also discussed. The need to change patriarchal farm identities and cultural norms was discussed. This could be supported through greater financial incentives for women to manage farms.
- *The importance of context to the right policies:* A wider issue was also discussed around how to tackle changing gender norms related to caring responsibilities. For example, should social norms around caregiving responsibilities be tackled by measures that work to change values and norms? Or can a policy that supports both men and women equally to take time off for parental caring responsibilities be the way forward, as illustrated by the Swedish system of shared parental leave? It was discussed how the way forward may depend on national cultural contexts and the extent of traditional caring gender norms. It was also discussed that if policy support for shared, paid parental leave is the route taken, changes to norms still do take time. Potentially this is a generational change rather than a short-term one.
- *The need for a culture shift around work culture – it is okay to take time off:* Beyond gender norms related to caring responsibilities, the issue of work-related social norms in farming and entrepreneurship also emerged as an issue. Taking time off should be normal practice, as it is for employees, and not the exception. The discussions also noted how this time can be regenerative and gives space for reflection and learning, also benefiting innovation.
- *Interconnections with wider issues of cooperation and shared ownership versus individual and private ownership:* Discussion emerging from this group also focused on the role of communal systems of farming such as Community

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Supported Agriculture where consumers pay in advance or associations involving landowners in forestry owning and working land together. It was discussed how these approaches could potentially play a role in reducing individual burdens and allowing for time off for various needs. The culture issue of a more common tendency towards private landownership, as well as deep attachment to land, was discussed as challenging these types of systems. Laws that provide a framework for cooperative landowners, and adjustment to land ownership laws by the government, were discussed as one way forward.

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